

Roadmap for Local Committee Construction

WP1

Better paths towards the governance
of radioactive waste

Antwerpen
2006

Berlin
2004

Ljubljana
2005

Who we are COWAM 1 & 2: "COMMUNITY WASTE MANAGEMENT"

Strong societal opposition has been seen in Europe, as elsewhere, to the options developed for **radioactive waste management (RWM)**, creating social distrust and political blockage. Reinforcing democracy (inclusive participation) in the decision-making process is looked to as a means for developing solutions acceptable to all. There was a need for all the players to examine the **governance of RWM: how decision-making structures and processes can ensure excellence, independence, transparency, participation, and accountability.**

To help address the "democratic deficit" a **European network** was initiated to examine governance issues from the point of view of the local and regional communities currently or potentially concerned by RWM. **"Community Waste Management" (COWAM 1, 2000-2003)** carried out a collective reflection on ways to improve the **decision-making process (DMP).**

COWAM 1 worked to empower local communities through networking, to share experiences and to become involved in a fair and competent dialogue with RWM implementers, regulators and experts. Key local and regional actors from 8 European countries, implementers, regulators and experts in RWM successfully came together for this purpose. More than 200 partners were involved, with 2/3 representing some twenty local communities and NGOs. www.cowam.com

Local communities are sometimes contacted by national authorities or waste management institutions to consider the siting of a new RWM facility on their territory. Alternatively, they may be concerned by the plans for dealing with radioactive waste produced by nuclear installations to which they are already hosts (power plants or processing industries). COWAM 1 recommendations stressed the need for the early and inclusive involvement of local stakeholders in the DMP. Several areas were found in which progress is needed if RWM governance is to be improved.

The follow-on European project, **COWAM 2 (2004-2006)**, undertook participative research into these governance areas. COWAM 2 comprised an international consortium of nineteen

partners and aimed at broad involvement of actors from civil society. It had significant representation from local communities, elected bodies and NGOs, as well as social and natural scientists from outside RWM institutions together with traditional players such as the implementers of RWM, public authorities, experts and waste producers.

COWAM 2 provided a forum for mutual learning by these stakeholders and experts. More than forty stakeholder institutions were involved in fifteen thematic workshops and three international seminars.

COWAM 2 is perhaps the sole European RWM governance context in which the full spectrum of actors spoke on an equal basis and shared the conduct of affairs.

COWAM 2 involved fourteen countries: Belgium, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Netherlands, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and the UK as well as Japan and South Africa.

There were five COWAM 2 working groups or "work packages":

- ✓ Implementing Local Democracy and Participatory Assessment Methods (WP1)
- ✓ Influence of Local Actors on the National Decision-Making Process (WP2)
- ✓ Quality of Decision-Making Processes (WP3)
- ✓ Longterm Governance (WP4)
- ✓ National Insights (WP5).

The final reports from each WP are available from www.cowam.org

This Roadmap was developed by WP1. We have quoted some results from the other work packages, too. This Roadmap was finalized in Summer 2006.

Our goals for this Roadmap for Local Committee Construction

WORK PACKAGE 1 "IMPLEMENTING LOCAL DEMOCRACY AND PARTICIPATORY ASSESSMENT METHODS"

- ✓ To empower local people
- ✓ To provide advice for organizing and fortifying the local voice in decision-making
- ✓ To improve the local voice's chances to be heard
- ✓ To help clarify the relations between the different players in RWM governance (including relations between local citizens/residents and the people who represent them in the RWM process)

According to COWAM 2 WP2, these goals correspond to **best practice** in developing "Local Influence on the National Process"

COWAM 2 ROADMAP FOR LOCAL COMMITTEE CONSTRUCTION

Thinking about building a Local Committee?

In many European nations there is a strong new trend for communities to take an active role in decision-making through Local Committees (whether organized spontaneously or created by law). These committees allow elected people and interested citizens to participate in complex decision-making processes where science and societal concerns meet.

We find that this new trend is a positive and lively one, and suits the need for communities to get involved early in decisions that affect them.

Our Roadmap for Local Committee Construction is the product of collaboration among stakeholders from across Europe: local elected people and community representatives, agents from national institutions, and researchers. This collaboration took place over a period of 3 years (2004-2006) in a working group on "Implementing Local Democracy and Participative Assessment Methods". This working group was organized within the European research project "Community Waste Management" (COWAM 2) focusing on the governance of radioactive waste management. COWAM 2 is described inside the front cover. The list of our working group participants - from 8 countries - is found at the end of this booklet.

We are convinced that local people have an important voice to raise when national decisions are to be taken on local sites and facilities for managing the wastes of nuclear power production, medical and industrial uses of the atom, etc. After all, storage facilities will be placed on local territory and will have impacts on community life for years to come. Residents will "look after" the waste for generations.

With this Roadmap, we want to share our basic knowledge about committee building, and examples from our practice, with other communities who may face important decisions. We cannot offer a single path. Instead, this Roadmap reflects the diverse landscape of experience in Europe.

You will find different sorts of text in each chapter of this Roadmap. We discuss our main ideas in regular text (black ink). We highlight or summarize some of these ideas with diagrams, lists, or other "boxes". We illustrate our message with examples drawn from the local communities, federations and other stakeholders who participated in our working group or in COWAM. These examples (boxes in blue ink) are usually found in the right hand column of each page. The boxes are numbered, and you'll find the number in the main text to direct you to the example. Please look at the Annexes early, to know more about the local committees and other stakeholders who contributed these examples. Federations of committees are described on page 19.

In a few places, we give background information in the numbered boxes. When other COWAM 2 working groups have something important to say about our subject, we add a box with their results.

We hope that the Roadmap will stimulate your thinking. We hope that the examples we provide from our experience will help your community, and your partners in decision-making. ■

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Chapter 1

YOUR LOCAL CONTEXT

So, what is a Local Committee (LC)?

In this Roadmap we'll be focusing on committees formed in localities envisioning their role in the management of radioactive wastes. LCs are formed officially (by national law or arrangement), or spontaneously by residents. They provide a forum for community discussion on how waste is to be managed. The communities generally are solicited in a national program to site installations for storing wastes produced by nuclear production of electricity. The wastes may be of high, low or intermediate radioactivity. The issue is to develop a management concept that is both safe and acceptable to all the players—particularly, to the communities who will host the installation over generations. ❶

The LCs we will cite in this Roadmap are some of those formed in European localities represented in the COWAM programs—and in particular, those who participated in our working group on "Implementing Local Democracy and Participative Assessment Methods". COWAM is described inside the front cover of the Roadmap, and our participants, including the Local Committees who contributed examples, are listed in the Annexes at the end.

Local Committees allow the communities to play a role in shaping and/or monitoring the radioactive waste management (RWM) process. Some recommendations for this process, from another COWAM 2 working group, are provided in box ❷ on this page).

Local Committees gather and disseminate information, follow scientific research performed by other players, develop and deliberate on solutions to address community impacts of an installation, give recommendations to other players, monitor other players' performance, and all in all make some part of the many decisions involved in waste management. Community involvement through LCs corresponds notably to the European requirement, through the Aarhus Convention, of ensuring access to information and public participation in decisions concerning the environment. And it is an opportunity eagerly seized by elected authorities and concerned residents to shape their future.

We start our Roadmap with consideration of the context in which such LCs originate. In this chapter we list some of the features that may influence how the LC is formed and conducted. The Roadmap can be read without detailed study of this first chapter. Subsequent chapters will detail the points we find important for constructing and running the LC. Those points will be useful to communities considering the use of a LC to deliberate on any kind of complex, social and technical project.

The boxes in this chapter first explore what is meant by "local" in the case ▶

❶ *Radioactive waste must be isolated to protect humans and the environment from the effects of radioactivity. Depending on its category, the waste remains dangerous over tens, hundreds or thousands of years. Managing the waste involves developing a technical storage concept, and siting, constructing, filling, then closing and monitoring the installation—a process involving many players, decisions, and years. In this perspective, we have to pay attention not only to the technological parts, but also to developing a robust and acceptable decision-making process, including ways for local people to raise their voice and participate actively.*

❷ **The COWAM 2 working group** on "Quality of Decision-Making Processes" has made recommendations that should be followed on a general level by national actors, but also, local players in their LC:

- Define goals (involve people in defining what has to be decided or done)
- Always provide alternatives (deciding is choosing among them)
- Ensure weighting and balancing of values and interests (don't leave out viewpoints)
- Be comprehensive (safety is foremost but not the only issue)
- Proceed stepwise (identify phases and check decisions before proceeding)
- Ensure flexibility (be sure an early action does not close down a desired option)
- Be transparent and open (show what you are doing and how you take views into account)
- Allow sufficient time (foresee that the many steps cannot be compressed and people will have to be involved for years)
- Stick to the "rules of the game" (set agreed rules and if they have to be changed, agree that)
- Define roles and responsibilities (clarify the role and powers of each player)
- Ensure early and inclusive participation (involve and consult)
- Establish control of the process (someone has to drive it along) ▶

of LCs formed for radioactive waste management. Then we check off what we mean by "context", that is, the specific features that may influence the choices that are made. There are no strict rules for how context will shape events in your community, but it may be useful to talk about these different features as you develop your LC.

A Local Committee does not get formed in a neutral environment. It is embedded in its particular local and national context and this will have an influence on the design of the LC and indirectly, on its effectiveness and legitimacy. The COWAM program and this Roadmap emphasize the local level because historically, national radioactive waste management has had trouble taking local views and needs into account. In fact, RWM is a national issue that needs a local solution.

What do we mean by "local"?

In the context of siting a new RWM facility, "local" means potential host sites and corresponding communities. "Local" may also be defined as the communities who could be affected by RWM decisions, even if they are not hosts. "Local" may also mean larger regions, encompassing the wider geopolitical area in which particular communities may be situated. Local communities involved in many different types of nuclear activities (producing, processing or storing waste), and also nearby communities may consider they are stakeholders in the national RWM policy-making process. The persons and places affected vary according to the type of decision that is being taken. It is important for those affected to find their voice and ways of making themselves heard in the decision-making process. ③④

What do we mean by "context"?

Firstly we just mean the general decision-making context. The decision process at hand sets the life cycle of the Local Committee, which comes into existence at a certain point in the process and ends at another. As the process unfolds your LC may have to deal with differing specific tasks. ⑤

Usually the history of RWM will weigh on the context. That history often has produced a lack of trust between national actors and local actors, or shows lack of agreement on what it is important to achieve. Today, in many cases, a prior failure, or trust-destroying events have urged authorities to seek a more cooperative manner of working with the local public. This can mean that Local Committees are officially created, or that authorities are eager to work with existing or new local organizations.

The following chapters of the Roadmap show how LC's enhance your community's effectiveness and thereby influence your context for the future. ■

- ▶ ● *Adapt format to tasks (match tools and procedures to what you have to achieve)*
- *Allocate adequate resources (foresee what's needed to assemble information and act on it)*
- *Ensure continuity of structure and awareness (RWM is a multi-generation issue and you have to pass along the ability to take care of it)*
- *Create influence of stakeholders (give real power to affected players)*
- *Enhance well-being (build up the positive benefits for the community now and later)*

③ **In Germany**, the siting process study commission AkEnd pointed out that what is "local" should be defined by the people themselves, not by administrative boundaries. AkEnd proposed that the area that volunteers to host a RWM facility should be self-defining and calls it a "social, cultural and economic unit" with no clearly marked geographic borders.

④ **In France**, the ANCLI White Paper on local governance of nuclear sites underlines that "firstly, Local Committees take up the perspective of their local community and its residents. Secondly, through their members, LCs can draw on a bank of knowledge and skills specifically relevant to their region. These factors allow LCs to tailor their activities when monitoring nuclear sites, channeling the perspectives of elected representatives and members of the public from the same region into specific investigations."

⑤ **In France**, there are Local Information Commissions around all nuclear sites. Their history illustrates how different committees may be needed at different points. The Prime Minister's 1981 circular creating "Information Commissions attached to Power Stations" was an important development, which enabled local communities to discuss nuclear issues together with the site operators and official inspectorates. RWM, local coordination and information sharing bodies were created in the four departments acting as candidates to host an Underground Research Laboratory (URL). Their particular objective was to spread information about the scientific RWM research and the siting procedure. Finally, the CLIS de Bure was created by decree in 1999 when the government decided to build the URL in the township of Bure.

WHAT IS "LOCAL"?

"LOCAL" MAY BE DEFINED BY SCALE...

- ✓ The local administrative or governmental units directly affected by the RWM decision-making process
- ✓ The geographic area in which residents feel affected by the issue
- ✓ The geographic area that will see impacts from a RWM installation (including transport of waste)
- ✓ The scale of "what is local" should be defined by the people themselves
- ✓ Local people are interested by the experience of other localities, and may feel closer to a far-away site with the same issues, than they do to the centralized national decision-making level

...OR BY THE NATURE OF THE INSTALLATION

- ✓ Two main cases in which a LC may be formed:
 - places that have no RWM installation but may be under consideration to become a host site
 - places that already host some sort of RWM installation, or a waste-producing industry ⁶
- ✓ For example, a future installation under study might be:
 - close to a working nuclear plant (examples found in Sweden, Belgium)
 - connected to a nuclear plant now being dismantled (UK, Spain)
 - a RWM research laboratory (France, Hungary)
- ✓ The RWM installation may already exist or may even be full and closed for monitoring ⁷

"LOCAL" IS ALSO DEFINED BY HISTORY...

- ✓ Local people know a lot about their region, its natural characteristics and its history
- ✓ Past history in general influences local attitudes about hosting a national RWM site ⁸
- ✓ Past RWM history is also remembered ⁹
- ✓ Some communities already host nuclear installations and know a lot about them. LC members may be well-informed and trained in the issues
- ✓ For others the issues are new and unfamiliar

... AND GEOGRAPHY

- ✓ The geologic character of the underlying terrain orients the choice of site (some countries have different possible "host rocks" like granite or clay; seismic activity must also be considered)

⁶ In Spain, there have been three local information commissions (CLI) in Vandellòs. The first CLI responded to construction of a new nuclear power plant (NPP), and the second was created to respond to the dismantling process of the older plant. The present committee monitors the operational aspects of Vandellòs-II. Its brief is now to cover the demand for information with regard to the NPP and help maintain normal relations between the NPP and the neighboring citizens.

⁷ In Germany, France, Spain, Belgium, Hungary, Romania... working longterm or interim waste management/disposal installations are found. In France and the UK, some installations are already closed and being monitored.

⁸ In France, the eastern region now hosting an underground laboratory has traditionally been associated with memories of major World War I battles. Moving to a new technological identity is not "automatic".

⁹ In many European countries, some localities were considered in the 1980's (or earlier) for installation siting without any voice in the process.

ECONOMIC CONTEXT

LOCAL ECONOMIC STATUS, COMMUNITY IMAGE AND IDENTITY

- ✓ Is the region in decline or in expansion? Is there unemployment?
- ✓ What is the local identity? How can a RWM installation fit in? ¹⁰

IMPACT OF THE INSTALLATION

- ✓ What economic impacts will be felt? Will they be short-lived or long-term? ¹¹
- ✓ Will hosting a RWM facility have a negative impact on the region's commercial image?
- ✓ Can hosting be made into a positive development opportunity? ^{12 13}

SOCIAL CONTEXT

WHO ARE THE PLAYERS?

- ✓ Community forces: elected bodies, civil society organizations...
- ✓ Local population
- ✓ The institution that proposes the RWM facility (operator, applicant)
- ✓ Other nuclear industry players present in the region

RELATIONSHIPS AMONG THE PLAYERS

- ✓ Role given to the various players by the decision-making process
- ✓ Relations between the local players and the institution proposing the RWM facility
- ✓ Relations with other industry players
- ✓ Relations between the local authorities and other decision-making authorities (parliament, ministries...)

¹⁰ The COWAM 2 working group on "Local Influence on the National Process" found that when your region has a clear vision for future development you may be better organized and raise a stronger voice.

¹¹ In the U.K., there have been worries at Sellafield that hosting waste after decommissioning may be the end of prosperity, rather than an opportunity to renew the economic dynamism of the isolated region.

¹² In France, under the new 2006 RWM law a contract between the state, the waste producers and the local communities will be signed in order to help the local communities in defining a sustainable territorial development project. The regions affected by the underground research laboratory already receive compensation money, but today's LC, the CLIS de Bure does not have any mandate to influence how it is spent. Its role is simply to follow the RWM research process at the laboratory site.

¹³ In Belgium, local partnerships had a subgroup in which compensation issues were discussed. They worked out socio-economic projects to sustain the community and help it maintain the capacity to monitor a RWM installation over the generations. These projects were to be finalized by the local council after the federal authorities selected which candidate community would host the waste repository.

POLITICAL AND LEGAL CONTEXT

LOCAL RIGHTS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR PARTICIPATION

- ✓ Europe's Aarhus Convention gives rights to local communities to participate in decisions affecting their environment
- ✓ The national decision-making process includes required tools for consultation (public inquiries, strategic environmental assessment, environmental impact assessment)
- ✓ Are these tools sufficient and workable for local communities to express their views?
- ✓ Does the process create other opportunities for participation?

LOCAL DEMOCRATIC CULTURE AND EXPERIENCE

- ✓ Is there a tradition of decentralized, transparent decision-making? ¹⁴
- ✓ Are elected representatives traditionally the community decision-makers? Do they have to consult the townspeople, or do they possess delegated authority?
- ✓ Is there a tradition of local deliberation using committees with diverse membership?

CREATION OF A LOCAL COMMITTEE

- ✓ What events led to the decision to use a LC? (failure of a past, non-participative siting attempt? Precedent set in other planning processes?) ¹⁵
- ✓ Does the law foresee the creation of a LC? ¹⁶
- ✓ Is the LC an initiative of the local level or is it proposed by other authorities?
- ✓ Does the local level have the power to negotiate the mission and the format of the LC?

¹⁵ In Slovenia, detailed analysis of the failure of the early 1990's siting project showed that public participation was inadequate. Information about the project was insufficient, public participation in site selection was not established and public acceptance was not achieved. A new process has been engaged with guarantees that local communities can decide to participate in or withdraw from siting candidature. However, they have little influence on framing the national process itself. The operator ARAO was given the ability to form partnerships with local communities to discuss the RWM project. These LC's include elected people, and local residents. The local partnerships are not a decision-making political body. They will follow the siting process and make recommendations to the local council.

¹⁴ In Romania, people remember the national history of insufficient information about central decisions. Although officially dialogue has been opened since 1989, people often have the impression that decisions are a "fait accompli". This influences the view of the current RWM process. The situation in nuclear plant host community Cernavodă is complex, because decisions are to be taken about building both new reactors and a waste repository. The implementer ANDRAD was created only recently and has few personnel; they are not very present in the community and their communication program, while ambitious, was not started immediately. ANDRAD is tasked only with RWM but people don't separate the nuclear reactor and waste issues. The local authorities don't have enough information about how siting is to be decided and by whom; they are worried that all decisions are already taken without them. Trust must be established by a constant dialogue between local and national decision-makers. This is where a LC can come in useful. Another important role of a LC will be to gather and disseminate information. Both environmental health and socio-economic compensations are topics of high concern.

¹⁶ In Hungary, in response to failed attempts to site a L/ILRW repository, a new Atomic Energy Act was passed in 1996. According to the Act financial support may be provided for the establishment of associations of local governments and their activities aimed at monitoring and public information in areas affected by existing or planned nuclear facilities. The Act established the legal basis for providing financial incentives for host and neighboring municipalities that support a nuclear facility. As a result, four public information and control associations have been established near (i) an existing low and intermediate-level waste repository, (ii) a similar planned repository, (iii) an existing spent fuel temporary storage facility, and (iv) a planned high-level waste facility. In 2005 the Atomic Energy Act was amended. According to the amendments, the use of financial incentives provided for the associations is no longer restricted to public information and monitoring activities, but such funding can be applied for regional development purposes, as well.

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGES

- ✓ Declining population?
- ✓ High or low density?
- ✓ Large proportion of one age group (youth, pensioners)?

LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT NUCLEAR POWER AND WASTE

- ✓ Local/regional presence of nuclear facilities?
- ✓ Local familiarity with and knowledge about nuclear issues?
- ✓ Knowledge resources (expertise) among LC members
- ✓ Training and information needs

LIFE CYCLE ISSUES

RADIOACTIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT IS A LONGTERM UNDERTAKING

- ✓ The technical arrangements are meant to last for hundreds or even thousands of years
- ✓ The decision-making process and steps to implement RWM facilities will take years or decades
- ✓ Facilities might operate for 40 years then be monitored for 100–300 years
- ✓ Society today has to create the means to transmit a "safety legacy" to future generations 17

THE LC TAKES ITS PLACE AT A CERTAIN POINT IN THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS

- ✓ What does the decision-making process target? (options evaluation ? siting? implementation? decommissioning?)
- ✓ When does an affected locality come into view, making it meaningful to set up a LC?
- ✓ The LC may play a different role according to the various phases of the decision-making process
- ✓ The LC may use different techniques to address different tasks as they come 18
- ✓ The LC may have a defined lifetime or it may adapt to new phases and continue working

17 The COWAM 2 working group on "Longterm Governance" analyzed the meaning of "longterm" and found that we cannot dictate the form of tomorrow's society. Instead, our generation has to invent management and governance processes that can help pass on to the very next generation (and onwards in turn) a "safety legacy". This legacy is composed of knowledge, know-how, safety procedures, protection options, institutions and various resources. This legacy should equip the next generation (and onwards in turn) to continue managing the waste. The processes we invent today may well change with time. It's the responsibility of future generations to take them forward or reconsider and adapt them to their circumstances. The LC plays an important role in creating and transmitting part of this legacy. The transmission starts right away, through disseminating knowledge in the community and also, renewing committee membership over time.

18 The COWAM 2 working group on "Implementing Local Democracy and Participatory Assessment Techniques" commissioned a report on "Tools for local stakeholders: How to choose the participatory techniques you need". It shows how different phases of the decision-making process call for different techniques to be applied by the LC, to run their own discussions or to consult the public (see Annex 3 / summaries of all our working group reports).

Chapter 2

MISSION, MANDATE, AND ROLE OF THE LOCAL COMMITTEE

For those just starting out the issue of an appropriate identity for the Local Committee (LC) is obviously important. Existing LCs will almost certainly find that, as circumstances change, you will need to evolve.

The LC's identity reflects your context, your mission, role and mandate. For example, it is often the case that a LC originally received a name including the word "information", because many committees were created as a channel for information flowing from the "top", from the industrial site, from the national RWM process or from the authorities, towards the "bottom", the population. However, committees today are increasingly likely to take an active role in generating information and disseminating it in many directions. You assure a link between the population and other actors by consulting and/or representing the public. You monitor more or less closely the technical RWM program and you may play a significant role in shaping the RWM project. ①②

The **mission** of the LC will reflect the history of its origins and the intentions of its founders but what the LC actually does may well need development as your situation changes. The **role** of the LC in the decision-making process (DMP) may well alter over time. For example, where a LC was set up to disseminate information do you have, or do you need to take, the role of critic with respect to technical studies? Should the LC develop the role of providing a means for local people to voice such a critique? ③.

① **In France**, national legislation foresees local information commissions associated with each "risky industry" site, including nuclear and RWM sites. COWAM 2 members include the CSPI, and the CLIS de Bure. Each committee disseminates site and RWM information towards the community, trains its members to be more competent, orders counter-expertise, etc. Neither of these LC has a determining voice in the RWM process. However, their membership inputs expertise and defends the regional/local point of view.

The CLIS de Bure is mandated to follow the implementer's research. It takes no position for or against the laboratory or any future storage facility.

② **In Hungary**, the West Mecsek Public Information and Regional Development Association (before 2005: West Mecsek Public Information Association), an association established in the area of a planned high-level waste repository, counts nine member communities. The missions of the WMPIA cover public information about the site investigation process, monitoring of the process, raising environmental consciousness and fostering development in the affected settlements. The association aims to heighten public acceptance of the process. The leader of the association also makes attempts to influence decision-making at the national level; this local mayor is member of a Parliament Lobby Group.

③ **In France**, the National Association of Local Information Commissions (ANCLI) groups LCs concerned with nuclear sites in general. In their White Paper of 2005, they stated: "After 20 years' experience in monitoring and providing information, CLIs now wish to redefine their remit more clearly as a 'Broad mission of communication, monitoring and expertise concerning

LOCAL COMMITTEE ROLE

Loosen tensions in a community

De-escalate existing conflict

Raise the local voice in the national debate

Conduct continuous dialogue among actors involved in RWM governance

Provide an integrated vision of local issues

Provide a democratic proposal for local development

Review/critique technical program

Transmit to future generations the means, procedures and know-how they will need for longterm active participation in RWM

An early task is to clarify the mission of the LC. No exhaustive list of possible aspects can be made but it is useful to consider how your LC fits in the decision-making process.

- ✓ Is the LC just to gather information from the implementer/operator or central authorities and disseminate it to the community?
- ✓ Is it to give advice to the implementer/operator and/or to other decision-makers?
- ✓ Does it have decision-making authority, and can it be overridden by others?
- ✓ Does it have the ability to grant or refuse legal authorizations?
- ✓ Does it have the capacity to repeat some of the technical studies through commissioning independent studies or reports?

These competencies should be defined and negotiated from the start, and formalized in the written **mandate**. LC members will be more involved and motivated if you have a real potential to influence the decision-making process. This potential can be measured in the decision-maker's response to LC proposals and arguments. Sometimes this response seems inadequate, and so it is important to look at all the chapters of this Roadmap to learn how LCs—or federations of LCs—have achieved more influence. ④

Local partners in COWAM 2 consider that LCs are there to rebalance power, to act as a "counterweight" to other actors in the RWM governance process. Although the LC cannot replace the legal or safety authorities you can make important impacts on the situation, raising the local voice in the national debate and, ideally, getting national decision-makers to understand your issues and take them into account. ⑤ ▶

▶ *the operation of nuclear sites and their impact on public health, the environment and the economy, throughout their operational lifetime and beyond!"*

④ **The COWAM 2 working group** on "Local Influence on the National Process" stated important principles for a siting process: this must be based on a voluntary partnership between the local community and the national level, with balanced negotiation capabilities and cooperative working out of RWM projects, including their technical aspects. This partnership should work out integrated projects including both technical aspects and socio-economic provisions favorable to sustainable territorial development. Don't forget that the local population will play an important role in longterm vigilance across the lifetime of the RWM installation.

⑤ **In Romania**, the Cernavodă Local Committee was created with the intention of informing the public of Cernavodă about the impact of the presence of the nuclear facilities in the immediate vicinity (NPP and intermediate dry storage for spent fuel). The LC has become an important interface between the community and nuclear authorities in the goal of respecting the basic social agreement (local development, health and environmental protection). The LC plays the role of negotiator and influences decisions.

One of the most successful models seen among COWAM 2 participants is that of the Belgian Local Partnerships. These were formed in pre-candidate communities with the mandate to work out all the details of a repository project, integrating both technical and socio-economic aspects. ⑥

The local partnerships built up projects reflecting community requirements in order to accept a repository on their territory. They defined the preferred technical solution (in detailed research carried out with the implementer, who acted as a member of the partnership). They also defined all the accompanying social programs to ensure incentives, compensations, and structures to retain community control of the project over the long term (in consultation with members representing all the social forces of the township). This mission was formalized in the legal mandate, and the implementer agreed to uphold and respect the outcome project.

Final decision power lies outside the Belgian LC (the municipal council decides whether to go forward with site candidature on the basis of the integrated project, and federal authorities designate the final site). But the strong identity and role of the LC have been clear to all these decision-makers as well as to the people of the communities. ■

⑥ In Belgium, implementer NIRAS/ONDRAF was instructed by the federal government to cooperate closely with the people of existing nuclear host communities (or other candidates) in defining how a low-level radioactive waste repository could be integrated into the local socio-economic context. A consultation process was carried out by a university team: the various actors in each community were met to reach a common definition of the issues at the local level and to get feedback on a proposed LC methodology. This process ended up with a specific structure for the "local partnerships" as regards management and composition. Mol chose to call their LC Mol Consultation on Nuclear Waste or MONA, while Dessel's LC was called Study and Consultation on Radioactive Waste or STOLA. The partners worked out a low-level waste disposal project on the one hand and a social project on the other hand. In this way the LCs had a strong role in determining the shape of a potential future RWM undertaking. "Have we been respected? Yes, but we had to fight for it" said the leader of MONA at our Annual COWAM Seminar.

Chapter 3

QUESTIONS OF LEGITIMACY: COMPOSITION AND REPRESENTATIVENESS

The perceived legitimacy of a Local Committee (your proper right to act for the local population in RWM decision-making) is an important issue. Legitimacy usually turns on questions of composition (who is in the LC?) and representation (to what extent does that LC speak for the local people?)

Legitimacy may come from different mechanisms of **representation**:

- ✓ Members may draw legitimacy from a formal process relying on the typical use of representative democracy, **elected representativeness**, or you may reflect parts of the community who are differently affected by the RWM question (**demographic representativeness**).
- ✓ Alternatively activists who have not been chosen by a formal method may take the role of speaking out for a certain viewpoint, no matter how many people share that viewpoint (known as **thematic representativeness**).

All types of representation may be incorporated into a LC. ①

Note that there are differences between legal status and community legitimacy:

- ✓ A LC may be legitimate because it is created by or responds to the law but
- ✓ It may also be legitimate because it represents community diversity and defends community values and interests.

Not all local committees are recognized by the political establishment. In some contexts, local participation in RWM issues has been the result of the spontaneous self-organization of concerned citizens. Rather than looking first for a demographically representative composition, momentum is built by involving people with management talent for running the interactions with e.g. the political representatives, the national waste management institutions and the nuclear operator. ②③

Raising the local voice through thematic representativeness tends to come first, before you can ensure other types of representation. But relying on the efforts of "interested volunteers" can only go so far: LC members will need training, education, expert insights and so on.

The LC requires resources. To obtain these you need to plan to gain greater community legitimacy. Drawing elected participants and demographic representatives into the committee and also consulting the population can help here. So adjust your representation and hence your legitimacy, to reflect your mandate, your desired audiences and your context. ④ ▶

① **In France**, the 93-member *CLIS de Bure* includes representatives from the municipal government of each township with at least part of its territory included in a 10-km radius around the underground laboratory site. Elected representatives to regional and national parliaments as well as decentralized state administrators (prefects, ministry inspectorates) also have a seat, as does the laboratory director. Representatives are invited from civil society organizations including the local chambers of commerce or agriculture, unions (including laboratory workers), and environmental protection associations (including those opposed to the waste repository option). The model for composition is dictated by national law and evolved with practice.

② **In Spain**, the local mayor is the "natural" leader for setting up the local committee.

③ **In Romania**, local participation in RWM issues has been the result of spontaneous self-organization of concerned citizens. This has significant consequences for all other issues in local committee functioning. For instance, at the birth of the Cernavodă group, the question of representativeness simply boiled down to "all people who are willing to participate." The LC opens a needed discussion and creates a forum in which the discussion may take place. As time goes on and more actors join the discussion, the local committee may wish to work for more community legitimacy and for a specific legal status inside the RWM decision process.

④ **In Sweden**, the Oskarshamn municipal council felt strongly that the RWM question should be the responsibility of ▶

WHICH PRINCIPLES OF REPRESENTATION SHOULD GUIDE THE COMPOSITION OF YOUR LC?

Elected representatives?

Demographic proportions?

Thematic viewpoints?

A mixed composition?

DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS exist and may evolve over time

► When it comes to the actual **composition** of the LC you will need ways of selecting people. It is helpful to get an idea of who needs representation, by mapping the affected population in terms of their interests as well as geographically. You will also have to retain those you have recruited. Experience suggests that this will be a significant task! In particular, some LCs recognized that special efforts have to be made to enable more women to participate. Their typical social role in the household means that longterm participation in evening working groups may be hard to achieve. Yet their perspective, like that of other population groups, is valuable to the LC and can help make your work better reflect the community.

Whilst the size of the LC will probably be dictated by resources, including funds, the composition also raises issues of internal organization. For example do all members have an equal voice in proceedings? ⑤

There are differing opinions on the legitimacy in the decision-making process of voices raised outside the "official" LC. Do they speak for a sufficient mass of persons? Should all interests get their representation only inside the committee? One way to view the issue is this: The LC chooses its membership towards the goal of fulfilling its mandate. In this light not all themes will be represented on a LC. Some actors may feel they better fulfil their own legitimate societal role by remaining outside the committee. For instance, in multi-actor and regional committees, the safety authority may wish to remain apart. Journalists may wish to remain outside a LC even though invited to

► *the persons (the council) already elected by the population. The official thematic working groups are organized by the municipality. The members of the working groups constitute a broad local representation including politicians, NGOs, associations, industry etc. A full time project manager co-ordinates the work with support of expert consultants. About 50 people are involved. This local municipality project is funded with grants from the national Nuclear Waste Fund. Activists hold a parallel dialogue with the implementer and they too can apply to the Fund to support their participation.*

⑤ *In Hungary, LCs are made up of the affected local governments. Each local government delegates one person (typically the mayor) to the LC's decision-making bureau. Others can also be invited to the meetings of the LC (e.g., delegates of civil society organisations), but only local government delegates have the right to vote. Associations are led by the mayor of one of the participating municipalities (typically, but not necessarily the community hosting the planned or operating waste facility).*

participate. In each case, this distance makes it possible to maintain neutrality and to ask questions that perhaps will not be asked inside a committee. ⑥

It is important to seek members who provide representation of different points of view, and also, who can provide special insight or expertise. Sometimes this means recruiting persons whose professional experience can enlighten the LC discussion. In other cases, your LC will consult outside experts to get the needed insight.

Many LCs have noticed that gradually, all active members become experts of RWM. They therefore move away from their original role defined by community representation. To maintain legitimacy through a close link with community perceptions and wishes, you must check alignment through informing and consulting the population.

You also have to plan for the renewal of LC membership. Some members may leave the LC when their free time is reduced, and when the decision-making process lasts for many years, members may wish to retire. Especially in cases where the LC includes representatives from other local associations, you should have a recruiting committee to bring in new members in good time. A current member might serve as a mentor to each new recruit. ⑦ ■

⑥ *In Belgium, the safety authority was not a member of the LC. But regulators don't need to stay out of the picture totally. In the case of MONA and STOLA, Belgian regulator FANC was enabled to follow their work closely, attending the meetings of the working groups as an observer. FANC had full access to the reports of these groups, and was also invited as expert to give explanation about certain issues.*

So FANC didn't remain apart and still maintained neutrality.

One of the next steps in the search for a solution for the disposal of low and intermediate level short lived waste will be when implementer NIRAS/ONDRAF submits a dossier, based on the work of the partnership, to the FANC. FANC knows the dossier already and by following the LC work, they helped ensure that no great discrepancy with safety rules will be found.

Each partner understands that the role of the FANC is official as from the point when they receive the implementer's formal license application.

⑦ *In Belgium, the local partnerships were organized by the municipality. Each LC was composed of about 75 members. Their composition was prepared by a careful local study. University researchers helped "map" the community, identifying the different civil society organizations (associations) present. All were invited to send a representative to the partnership. An open call, too, was made for volunteers.*

Some members bring special expertise from their professional context: for instance, retired workers from the nuclear establishment came to the LC as local representatives well-informed on radiation protection issues. A local building contractor was able to help fellow STOLA members understand different options for engineering and tunneling in particular.

Chapter 4

FUNDING AND RESOURCES

Human and material resources will be needed for you to do your work and meet your mandate. Your LC will require adequate, sustainable funding support. You must be clear about where the money is to come from and who will be driving the process along. ❶

The participatory process requires the actual capacity for you to participate. If subject to limited resources it will be difficult for you and your community to make your voice heard. The key issue is that you have access to funding so that you can inform local inhabitants and develop your competence. These are needed in order for you to participate meaningfully. ❷

Training should be funded so that the local stakeholder members can develop enough background to have a grip on the situation. You need to be informed and to be able to inform the local population so that you can have a real influence on the different options and on the choices that will be made. ❸

Does the LC have the mandate to influence the technical and/or social choices and concepts? LCs depend on knowledge from diverse sources to reach a judgement considering all the relevant aspects. What expertise will be available? You may need the support of paid external experts when reviews or specific research are needed. This will be possible only if there is sufficient funding available.

Your efforts have somehow to be recognized and acknowledged. Some LCs decide that to maintain their community credibility the volunteer members should not be paid. The pure volunteer model is not the only option. In some contexts the LC will decide to pay the members for their time spent. Even more than paid members, as volunteers you will continue your hard work over

❶ **The COWAM 2 working group** “Local Influence on the National Process” stated: “Local authorities are major actors in the decision process and must benefit from resources sufficient to support their participation.”

❷ **In Slovenia**, three municipalities entered into legal agreements with the implementer ARAO (but two subsequently decided to opt out). Krško is going ahead with 3 signed contracts:

- a general agreement on forming a local partnership,
- a contract regarding financial compensation to the town for accepting a technical field investigation and
- a year-long engagement on local partnership obligations and activities (including the LC budget for that year).

Two funds directly concern the LC and its role. The LC receives 42 000 EUR annually for operations and for any studies it can afford. Furthermore, there are 84 000 EUR annually available for special studies too expensive to be paid for by the usual annual funds. Finally, the Contract of Agreement states that the LC can request that ARAO undertake and pay directly for appropriate studies.

❸ **In Sweden**, the Oskarshamn municipality when solicited by the implementer made two requests: that it be provided with financial resources in order for the local people to become a competent actor in the dialogue; that the technical feasibility study be discussed in a forum. Following this, legislation was enacted to enable the Government to provide an annual grant to all municipalities involved in feasibility studies. Potential siting municipalities may build up expertise or consult experts on their own. How the money is used is left up to the local communities. The grants are financed from the assets of the national Nuclear Waste Fund (which had been set up much earlier) ▶

FUNDING NEEDS

Do you have access to funding that

allows you to inform local inhabitants and

develop a competence of your own that

provides you with the tools for meaningful participation?

months and years only if you can see that the LC is able to make a difference and that decision-makers respect your input. While effective influence depends also on the legal status granted to the LC within the decision-making process, gaining a satisfactory degree of influence will be difficult without sufficient material resources to do your work properly and make it known. ④

LC participation is a time-consuming commitment. While institutional actors take care of RWM activities on their paid time, community members participate "alongside" other professional and household duties, often in evening and weekend sessions. Some LCs found that women, because of their typical household role, had a harder time sustaining their participation. Single parents are faced by the same issues. It may be necessary to make special provisions for childcare and household help to allow valuable members to continue making their contribution. All LC members will need assurance that travel and other expenses are covered.

A dedicated budget should pay for LC actions. If there is a genuine will to empower the community to take part in the decision-making process, institutions must earmark sufficient funds to finance local involvement. Funds may come directly from authorities such as a Nuclear Decommissioning Authority, a Radioactive Waste Authority or the Environment Ministry. Similarly money may come from local government or the applicant for the repository or laboratory. Sometimes LCs are jointly funded. Funds may be based on the 'polluter-pays principle' and collected through a surcharge on electricity consumption or a tax on nuclear operators. ⑤

Some budget examples may be provided.

In Belgium, in order to allow the local participants to work independently, each LC received federal funds of approximately 250 000 EUR annually through implementing agency NIRAS/ONDRAF. On top of that a purse of 150 000 EUR was set aside for the elaboration of the project proposal and for socio-economic studies. This purse was managed by the executive committee. The annual budget served to cover general expenses such as the salaries of the project coordinators, all communication activity and all 'operational ▶

▶ in order to secure the financing of costs in connection with permanently taking care of Swedish spent nuclear fuel etc.). The Fund is accumulated by the waste producers based on the polluter-pays principle (a surcharge on nuclear-generated electricity).

The municipalities strongly believe that it is the elected representatives of each locality who are the "natural" participants and decision-makers. The funding arrangements support this role.

④ In Scotland, a Local Stakeholder Group (LSG) has been created to accompany the phase-out and dismantling process. This group's "identified allowable expenses", including administrative support will be funded by the Nuclear Decommissioning Authority (NDA) through the site contract and budget. LSG activities and their associated costs will be included in the Near Term Work Plan and be subject to review. Members of the LSG will be entitled to claim out of pocket expenses to attend meetings. The LSG will also consider legitimate claims for additional expenses on a case by case basis. The NDA will be prepared to consider the payment of an honorarium to the holder of the Site Stakeholder Group Chair.

⑤ In Hungary, the West-Mecsek Public Information Association is funded through the polluter-pays principle. Funding is not compensation, ▶

KEY QUESTIONS

Who is paying and who should be paying?

Who is managing, who is driving the process?

Are committee members paid?

WHO PAYS?

National government department?

Local government or municipality?

Implementer or applicant for the facility?

National project authority or similar?

Independent fund based on 'polluter-pays' principle?

► costs' (stationary, telephone bills, mailings, electricity...), as well as logistic support for the working groups. This 'logistic support' should be interpreted in the broadest possible way. Apart from serving the volunteers coffee and biscuits during their working group meetings, it also allowed them to invite the experts of their choice, to order the studies they thought necessary and to pay for site visits or other relevant trips or conferences. The fact however that the partnership budget could be used to order research or studies does not mean that all research activity had to be paid for by the partnerships. Necessary research with regard to the technical and safety aspects of the repository facility remained NIRAS/ONDRAF's responsibility. The partnerships could decide they needed additional research in certain areas or wanted a second opinion. Such expenses as a rule also fell under the responsibility of NIRAS/ONDRAF. The research not directly related to such repository aspects was paid for by the partnership out of its dedicated fund (Hooft et al., 2002, *Local partnerships: Achieving stakeholder consensus on low-level waste disposal?* Presentation at WM-02, Tucson; p. 6).

In France, the CLIS de Bure operates on an annual budget of 305 000 EUR funded by the Ministry of Economy and Finance. This pays the salaries of a full-time general secretary, a scientific secretary and an administrative secretary (each part-time), and for operating the CLIS office at Bure and stocking an open-door reading room with relevant literature (meeting rooms are provided by the Prefecture). Each year the CLIS Bureau defines a program of activities also funded by the budget. This includes monthly Bureau sessions, periodic plenary sessions, training seminars for the members, information and training meetings open to the public (expert talks, colloquia...), publication and dissemination of CLIS documents, a website, information campaigns (posters, mailings, announcements in the press and by radio, traveling exhibits...). Members may travel to relevant RWM sites in France and abroad, and attend national and international meetings. Agreed expenses for members' travel to regular CLIS sessions, other meetings and site visits are reimbursed. The CLIS may also spend out of this budget to commission independent experts. Unspent monies from each year's budget are placed in reserve for the following year in order to build up available cash for such research.

Independence is vital. Funding mechanisms should be constructed in a way that guarantees LC independence from the implementer. It follows that independent financial funding should be externally audited and transparently managed.

Local authorities and LCs find it very useful to join forces in national or international federations. These networks allow its members to benefit from others' experience. They can become strong players on the national or international scene, and thereby consolidate local influence. The federations mutualize resources: local communities can address questions to experts within the network, and the federation can engage broad research, consultation and expertise of value to all members. Federations in Europe are described on the next page. ■ ⑥

► *but a negotiated portion of the site investigation project costs, dedicated originally to necessary information and communication activities, but now with recent legal changes also to regional development purposes. Funding also covers administrative expenses.*

⑥ **The COWAM 2 working group** on "Local Influence on the National Process" highlights this good practice: "Formation of networks among local communities (through national and European federations) helps gain structured influence of the local level on the decision-making process and reinforces their position".

The working group also recommends, as part of the national landscape, forming a National Integration Body that includes the different actors and in which the local and regional authorities are represented. This high committee should have an official role in the decision-making process in order to ensure true influence of local and regional collectivities. It will provide democratic control of the process, in a complementary way to the role played by traditional parliamentary bodies. It can act as "guardian" of the process and ensure that the process is transparent.

Networking and federations

In France, ANCLI (*National Association of Local Information Commissions*) is a grouping of LCs associated with power stations (as defined by the 1981 Circular by Prime Minister Mauroy) and other LCs attached to nuclear or waste sites. ANCLI was created in 2000 as a network for mutual information and exchange among LCs, using a newsletter, website, visits, colloquia, etc. Each LC sends up to four delegates. The ANCLI acts as an interface with national institutions, provides logistical support and training to LCs, and carries out studies and expertise on environmental protection and nuclear safety (undertaken or supervised by the Scientific Committee). ANCLI offers a forum for developing proposals and suggestions agreed by the LCs. For instance, the Mauroy Circular gave the LCs a legitimate existence but provided no solid legal status or funding opportunities (the LCs have relied on volunteer efforts and funding granted by regional government and the Finance Ministry with support by the Safety Authority). The ANCLI therefore developed a "White Paper on Local Governance of Nuclear Sites" making specific proposals to the national parliament on giving LCs a workable status, a funding basis and appropriate powers. A "White Paper on Radioactive Waste Management" is under preparation.

www.ancli.fr

In Spain, AMAC (*the Association of Municipalities in Nuclear Plant Areas*) was created in 1988 in Tarragona. It provided the first structured contact between municipalities situated in the 10 kilometer radius of a nuclear power plant (NPP). These municipalities, included in the Nuclear Emergency Plans, decided to create the association due to the deficiencies in emergency planning and preparedness and the impact of the NPP on the socio-economic development of their geographic area. Now enlarged to 68 municipalities affected by nuclear installations, AMAC represents the local authorities in national discussions of nuclear governance and RWM. The association provides support for local monitoring of NPPs, for the implementation of Nuclear Emergency Plans and for the creation of effective plans of economic development, and member municipalities have obtained clear improvements in these areas. AMAC promoted and helped create Local Committees of Information (one in each NPP area) in order to keep citizens informed of all matters related to the nuclear installation. The association promoted a special edition of COWAM 2, "Cowam Spain", in order to let municipalities participate effectively in the RWM decision-making process. Cowam Spain has been successful in promoting cooperation between the RWM players on the national and local levels, working out policy recommendations grounded in the democratic ideals of transparency, information and participation.

www.amac.es

In Europe, GMF (*Group of European municipalities with nuclear facilities*) was founded in 1993 to defend European nuclear municipalities and ensure that they take part in the existing discussion forums and in processes of decision-making in the European Union. GMF organizes annual meetings allowing municipal authorities and elected people to gather and exchange information about the nuclear situation in each European country (including safety and future plans) and about municipal experience regarding territorial planning, economic development and civil protection. The group helps its members (including those in new European Member States) become better integrated in the Union. Major themes include: a sustainable future for the community after plant decommissioning through early economic capacity development; nuclear waste management and storage; developing local democracy.

www.gmf-europe.org

In Europe, EUROCLI is a network created in 2006 by federations of local government or LCs in France, Great Britain, Romania and Spain, joined by Belgium and Slovenia, to get involved in nuclear decision-making on the European level. EUROCLI will form a European association that can form contractual relationships with the European Commission and request funding for its activities. EUROCLI will allow its members to grow in competence through exchanging experience and formal expertise. The network will undertake research on tomorrow's nuclear governance. It will develop a shared political strategy. It will write a charter on good practice in applying the Aarhus Convention to nuclear decision-making. EUROCLI will help local authorities in other European countries to learn about democratic progress in nuclear governance.

www.ancli.fr

Chapter 5

ORGANIZATION AND PROCEDURES

The organization of the LC, its internal structure and duties, will reflect your mission and mandate. From the outset, you will have to adopt appropriate procedures to facilitate the principal activities that are envisaged. ❶

There is no standard blueprint for a Local Committee. Although some elements may be useful in all circumstances, you will need flexibility to deal with the likely evolution of the LC role over its lifetime. At each stage it may be helpful to think through a list of questions about the respective powers and connections between your eventual sub-units. Our key questions below are inspired by the organizational charts provided in this chapter by three LCs, each one showing an executive body and subgroups.

KEY ORGANIZATIONAL QUESTIONS

What are the powers:

- ✓ of the Chair?
- ✓ of the Executive Committee/Council...?

What are the responsibilities of each group?

What is the appropriate procedure:

- ✓ for your general meeting?
- ✓ for approval of the Chair?
- ✓ for selecting the Executive Committee?

What is the frequency

- ✓ for general meetings
- ✓ for group meetings...?

What groups will you need and what links should exist between them?

How can you ensure co-operation?

How can you keep everyone "up to speed" when some work constantly in sub-

groups, and others are simply members of plenaries meeting less often?

How will the LC connect with the decision-making process?

What procedures will produce and spread the information for groups, the community, media or national authorities?

How will you arrange:

- ✓ budget approval and reporting?
- ✓ evaluation of your activity?
- ✓ annual report approval?

❶ **In France**, the CLIS de Bure bureau considered a detailed rule for how many minutes members could speak, how response time would be counted, etc. However, they decided not to create a formal rule. Bureau discussions are therefore very free. This means that the Chair must have the personal talent to channel discussion, to be sure those who wish it are able to get the microphone, and so forth. It also means that all bureau members have to be willing to listen—and to express themselves. You have to speak up if you want your viewpoint to be known. And it's better to explain your reaction to another's viewpoint, than to remain silent.

❷ **In Belgium**, MONA's experience shows that it is important to think about the deliberation process from the committee members' standpoint and consider arrangements that allow sufficient time. Politicians tried to speed up the process and volunteers were dropping out because there was too much time pressure. This was a low point in the LC experience - the municipal council at one time even wanted to abolish the LC.

One issue may be meeting deadlines set by others. Often institutional documents are announced for review before they can be delivered and because the LC is the weakest partner it can hardly force others to grant a correspondingly extended deadline to respond.

You should bear in mind that other bodies (local government, national authorities...) will likely impact your activities by requesting reports, giving deadlines, requiring meetings.... This impact can be handled by organization/re-organization of your procedures. ❷

The organizational structure of MONA is shown on the next page. It was arrived at after a considerable debate involving local stakeholders and implementer NIRAS/ONDRAF, which participates as the solitary non-local member.

MONA (Belgium) Organizational Structure

CLIS DE BURE (France) Organizational Structure

KRŠKO (Slovenia) Local Partnership Organization

► MONA's General Assembly brings together representatives from each of the participating organizations. It sets the strategy and delineates the main points to be addressed in the subsequent discussions. It also appoints the Executive Committee, which has charge of the day-to-day management of the organization. It is the Executive Committee that decides on budget spending and supervises the two full time Project Coordinators. The leaders of the thematic Working Groups are part of the Executive Committee and together they discuss and set group activities. The Working Groups contain representatives from the founding organizations as well as local people who voluntarily participate. They discuss all the relevant aspects of the repository project (both technical and socio-economic), take account of existing research and evaluate the need for additional studies. They can call on independent experts as necessary. They report regularly to the Executive Committee. Logistical and administrative support is provided by the Project Coordinators, who are employed full time by the partnership.

Another example is illustrated by the organizational diagram of France's CLIS de Bure. This Committee on Local Information and Monitoring is associated with the underground research laboratory operated at Bure by implementer ANDRA as part of the national research program on waste management solutions. The CLIS has a more heterogeneous membership than does MONA, representing a more extended territory. The CLIS is composed of representatives of the state and chambers of commerce and industry, industrial and agricultural unions (including RWM lab workers' unions), environmental protection associations, and elected representatives (national and local). Because the township of Bure is located close to the border of two territorial units (departments), each of these as well as the General Council of the two administrative regions in which they lie is represented on the CLIS. Elected people from townships lying within 10 kilometers of the site are members, as is the director of the ANDRA laboratory. The structure of the CLIS was defined by law and worked out in practice. The appointed Chair of the CLIS is a state Prefect, while the Vice-Chair is a regional elected representative. They oversee meeting agendas and keep parliamentary order. The CLIS holds three or four plenary sessions every year that are open to the public and the media. It holds eight or nine Board sessions per year gathering a core group of delegates elected by the entire CLIS membership. Another type of body within the CLIS is the Working Group. Currently there are five. Each is formed around a theme and participants are drawn from the Board and the general CLIS membership. The CLIS also benefits from three salaried workers. The General Secretary works full time as coordinator and prepares minutes and other correspondence. A part-time assistant provides logistical support. The part-time Scientific Secretary reviews technical and scientific documents and helps CLIS members formulate their questions to the RWM agency and other experts.

In Krško, the local partnership is centered on five Thematic Committees, whose membership is open to any Krško citizen. Operations are structured by a Coordination Committee. This includes two elected council members, the Mayor or his representatives, and representatives from outside the township: nearby affected communities and the implementer ARAO. The Coordination Committee also has five seats for delegates from the five Thematic Committees; these delegates are elected by their committee according to the agenda to be discussed in any given Coordination meeting. The five groups deliberate on matters important to Krško and also to the work of the LC itself; for instance, the Aarhus Convention group studies how this treaty can shape the action of the local partnership over time. All participants are part of a General Assembly, supported by a secretary paid by the Municipality from the LC operating budget. ③ ■

③ In Slovenia, local partnership contracts were signed between mayors in the affected communities and implementer ARAO. For the mayors one big issue is the articulation between the future LC and municipal decision-makers. This is the first time the local level has had a role in a national process so how will local politicians regard the LC? Will they perceive it as usurping their authority? Will they try to influence the LC or become involved in it? To address such issues the mayors want to get all local political parties to agree the "rules of the game", the right LC format and internal function to ensure the partnership will be a true collaboration. Questions include: the role and powers of the LC; who should be on it; how to represent all the diversity; what to do if no one wants to participate? The partnership must fit in too with current relations between the council and the nuclear power plant. The mayors know they must manage a total context - they are not concerned only with waste, like ARAO. For this reason, when setting up their LC the representatives must think about overall community goals and ambitions.

Creating Krško's local partnership has been the occasion to build new understanding of the community's future. At the beginning, says the mayor, public meetings were held to discuss the partnership concept. But people mostly wanted to debate about individual compensation for the restrictions a waste management site might place on their land. For four months, it seemed there was conflict; then, people agreed that a LC with thematic committees would be useful to talk together about their common interest. The target shifted from money-talk to mutual education. The local partnership will take 3 years to deliberate about where the best site might be within community lines. And the municipality will integrate this deliberation into a forward-looking industrial and economic development plan.

Chapter 6

INFORMATION, EXPERTISE, KNOWLEDGE BUILDING AND TRANSFER

The governance of RWM is complex and seems to work best when the issues are looked at from a great variety of standpoints. This is true for the scientific issues and for the societal issues. Stakeholders and experts from different areas all have to express themselves and cooperate across the lines that usually separate them. Knowledge does not just exist "objectively", independently of the actor. The different participants have to build up the diverse knowledge that is needed to understand the issues and develop the solutions. Consequently the LC will often need to draw on different types of expertise, including "counter-expertise" (independent checking of knowledge provided by other actors) and "citizens' expertise" (knowledge and viewpoints that institutional players may not have).

We have listed some "prerequisites for knowledge building" in the box at the bottom of this page. These are elements that we think any LC needs to start the ball rolling and keep it in play. You will need mechanisms for the Committee members to get information, to acquire knowledge and to use it properly. For example, you will need to develop the technique of asking the right questions of the technical experts and you will need to teach them how to talk to you in ways that you can understand. ❶

While one of the LC's functions is to generate information about local viewpoints, you will always depend as well on experts and gathering knowledge from "outside". Don't hesitate to consult, wherever necessary, experts of your LC's choice. Many LCs have obtained a specific fund for studies and expertise, and federations mutualize their resources for this purpose. ❷ ▶

❶ **In Belgium**, STOLA members found that invited experts gave very general elementary talks. STOLA had to explain that they were not a social club, but that they needed specific information to further their role in shaping the technical repository characteristics and to consider safety requirements. They learned that clear terms of reference had to be given along with the invitation to speak, and they prepared their questions carefully.

❷ **In France**, the President of the ANCLI Scientific Committee told the National Debate on RWM how LCs and their federation could play a primary role in the difficult task of checking scientific facts:

- Getting competent people from each site or community to join forces in the federated Scientific Committee to benefit all LCs across the territory
- Pooling money to obtain expert evaluations
- Using an agreement with the research arm of the national Safety Authority to get their expert support
- Insisting on freedom of access to technical documents ▶

WHAT DO YOU NEED TO BEST BUILD UP KNOWLEDGE?

- ✓ **The right attitude:** be assured that you and your understanding are vital to the governance process. Be aware of sources for building your knowledge and be willing to develop understanding in difficult areas.
- ✓ **Clear boundaries:** for expertise of any kind you need to ask, "Who has the competence to give us the information we need? What are the limits of a given expert? What might be his/her interest?"
- ✓ **Time, commitment and material resources**
- ✓ **Access to information which has a transparent pedigree and can be traced to its source**
- ✓ **Procedures to sort information, to evaluate knowledge and gaps in knowledge, and to share it within the LC and the community**

GOOD IDEAS FOR YOUR KNOWLEDGE BUILDING PROCESS

- ✓ Bring people into the LC who already know the issue, other actors' arguments, and/or the specialists' language
- ✓ Make it clear to consulted experts that an expert has to learn as well. Learning is mutual
- ✓ Use a stepwise and recursive procedure (following an agreed, planned series of steps, and checking success at each stage) in order to enhance the quality of expertise and decisions

▶ We give some tips in a box on this page for getting the most out of experts and specialized knowledge. For instance, it can be very helpful if your LC recruits members or staff who know how to speak the experts' language, and who are interested in "translating" it into language all the other members can understand.

No single party can achieve everything alone. Trust has to be established as a partial substitute for your own limited knowledge: there must be mutual trust among partners (experts, committees, institutional stakeholders...) and the belief that someone can bring reliable information to fill in a particular gap. Trust will be built on credibility, authenticity, on the consistency and coherence of argumentation as well as on behavior in harmony with these. To build up trust, you should follow your own rules well, and require of all parties that they respect and fulfill their own role in the best way possible. And you should tell other parties when their action is helpful and useful to the LC. ③

Just collecting information is not good enough. It has to be digested and integrated into your reflection and conclusions. In short, information must become knowledge, and common knowledge at that. There is little point in a few committee members becoming specialists if they are the only ones to know about an important aspect. You need a dialogue format to facilitate learning and discussing the knowledge you are gathering.

When you are ready to share what you have learned, remember that dissemination of information and transfer of knowledge are different processes.

- ✓ In dissemination the main purpose is to make information accessible to the public or other target actors.
- ✓ In knowledge transfer the aim is to enable persons (such as LC members) to perform specific activities.

Different methods may be best to accomplish these two tasks (see the box below). ■

▶ *in order to exercise democratic vigilance and control and thereby help protect the population*

- *Bringing together representatives of LCs to exchange experience and knowledge*

③ **In Belgium, the Fleurus and Farciennes municipalities at first refused to establish a local partnership and requested proofs of technical feasibility from NIRAS/ONDRAF. However, they did accept a discussion forum to convey information to the people. A university team led this forum with NIRAS/ONDRAF engineers. In the three-year forum NIRAS/ONDRAF experts were open in sharing their uncertainties and doubts, making it possible to integrate questions, doubts and concerns expressed by the local population into the final concept definition. Moreover, the population offered valuable information about relevant technical conditions: past mining activities, soil and watercourses. With this experience, in which experts and community representatives learned to trust each other and their specialized knowledge, the municipalities agreed to form a local partnership.**

DISSEMINATION OF INFORMATION

MECHANISMS FOR INFORMATION DISSEMINATION

- ✓ reports
- ✓ posters
- ✓ web sites
- ✓ newsletters
- ✓ video
- ✓ seminars and public debates

AND TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE

MECHANISMS FOR KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

- ✓ expert presentations followed by detailed questions and answers
- ✓ workshops
- ✓ training and e-learning

INFORMATION FLOWS 4

QUESTIONS TO ASK ABOUT DIALOGUE BETWEEN EXPERT AND COMMUNITY PARTNERS

- ✓ Is the informant trustworthy? Is the information complete? Is the knowledge robust? Does it add to the solidity of our conclusions?
- ✓ Do we have an agreed dialogue process to protect the LC, and the relationships it forms with others, from obstacles, frustrations and difficulties?

TRANSFERING KNOWLEDGE 5

- ✓ The success of the transfer mainly depends on the cooperation and willingness of dialogue partners to share their knowledge – the methods used are usually secondary.
- ✓ Traditionally knowledge is passed from mouth to ear with little permanent record. And when knowledge bearers leave an organization, they take all their expertise with them. Find ways for LC members who leave to transfer enough of their knowledge to the remaining members.
- ✓ Remember the power of the Internet for information transfer between LCs in different countries and regions.

4 In France, there are several procedures for the CLIS de Bure to transmit questions to ANDRA about the laboratory research program. First, during monthly Bureau meetings, members can informally pose their questions and the laboratory director (ANDRA's member-representative to the CLIS) either answers directly or promises to send the information. If the response is not received, then the Chair addresses a formal letter of request to the laboratory or to ANDRA's head office. Similarly, between meetings members can tell the General Secretary of a question they may have, and this is forwarded to ANDRA by e-mail or letter. The implementer needs to have a written trace of such questions to meet ANDRA's own quality assurance procedure. Finally, at each Bureau meeting there is a scheduled presentation by ANDRA or another scientific or technical player. This may highlight research progress, or analyze a specific report, or respond in detail to a complicated question posed earlier in the year. The Scientific Secretary of the CLIS is another resource, reading and analyzing pertinent documents, or helping to formulate Bureau questions.

5 In Belgium, the local partnerships built a well-organized archiving system so that all the documents they examined or produced will be available to others. In this way, their reasoning can be verified and understood. Here's an example of checking knowledge and making it transparent for others. MONA had to deliver an integrated waste repository concept (or concepts) to the Mol Municipal Council, and make a recommendation to the Council ('accept' or 'do not accept' to host the project). MONA wanted to review their concepts before delivery, to be sure they were complete, to control their quality, to be able to justify each element of the concepts, and to check that no element (positive or negative) was "counted twice" when they prepared their recommendation. With the help of research institute SCK-CEN, MONA undertook a Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA). Each element or characteristic of MONA's repository concepts was identified, and then judged on criteria (also developed and refined during the MCA exercise). MONA found that:

- The structured method highlights individual differences in judgement but also lets you seek consensus or at least agreement on an alternative
- Using MCA is a learning process and requires strong engagement from participants over a series of meetings. It also has value as a team-building exercise and some wished it had been undertaken earlier, for this reason
- Safety came out as the most important single judgement criterion, but it was by no means the only one

Some new ideas or concerns were raised in the MCA meetings, but including them in the analysis did not change the conclusion. This showed that the general concept or framework already developed by MONA was substantially complete or reflected the most important elements for decision-making.

WHO ARE THE EXPERTS AND WHAT CAN THEY DO? 6 7

- ✓ Experts are necessary but not sufficient. They are not the decision-makers.
- ✓ Experts are, by definition, experts in only a narrow field, so they are 'lay people' in other fields just as community LC members are.
- ✓ LC members are also experts – of everyday life and of views in your community. You should check to be sure you are well aware of those views.
- ✓ The experts will leave whereas you, and fellow community members, will stay.

6 In France, the CLIS de Bure has the power to conduct (or commission) independent review of the ANDRA research program. The working group concerned with monitoring the program obtained agreement from the Bureau and Plenary to develop a brief for external expertise. This was published in French and European Official Journals according to European rules. Eight expert organizations, from Europe and North America, requested the brief. The working group then defined the detailed terms of reference and published a call for tender under French rules. One organization replied under the official call and was selected to conduct the scientific review of ANDRA's work. The CLIS considered this to be a valuable exercise. Not only did they receive detailed review information, but also, they demonstrated that they were playing their monitoring role. The counter-expertise report was published and widely disseminated to the CLIS' institutional partners. The regional press often refers to the report. However, response from other partners has been disappointing: there was little consideration or re-publication of the review. The CLIS finds it noteworthy that of all national institutions, only the National Commission for Public Debate took the independent review into account, and referred to it in constructing the 2005/2006 consultation on RWM.

7 In France, the IRSN steered its research into new directions in response to some questions about Bure by members of the public or by the CLIS. For instance, the local press relayed concern about whether a sustainable form of energy, underground hot water/hot rock resources, might exist at Bure. Although this was not identified elsewhere as a crucial issue for evaluating the feasibility of building a repository at Bure, the IRSN as public experts decided to look into the geothermal potential of the area. Similarly, while the point has been judged secondary in the feasibility file, the IRSN may decide to look further into the seismic characteristics of the area so as to be able to provide the expertise called for by civil society.

Chapter 7

PRODUCT, OUTPUT, ADDED VALUE

The LC is accomplishing valuable work through its "daily" activities. You are providing a forum for dealing with ideas that the community finds important. The LC seeks and applies solutions to the issues confronting your community. You will be looking for ways to make the work concrete, visible to others and influential.

While developing your LC mission statement and budget forecast, you should consider tangible and intangible products and outputs. These may include services to the community (like fact-finding, or representing interests). They may include services to decision-makers (like reports, presentations, or recommendations). ①

The LC is viewed by communities as an extra tool for local democracy. Normally, most questions of local interest are addressed by the usual elected representatives of the people. From this perspective, the RWM debate too could take place within the municipal council. A siting or repository project could be addressed by a council sub-committee with the help of some experts and local notables. However, our working group members found that with such complex and difficult issues it may be better to form a LC, as a specific discussion forum. Within the LC, there may be more serenity, more focus, and the opportunity to incorporate more viewpoints. ▶

① In Belgium, STOLA published its final report after 4 1/2 years of volunteer work by 76 members of the community. It is entitled "Belgian low-level and short-lived waste: Does it belong in Dessel? – An integrated disposal project with technical and social implications; Choosing a sustainable solution".

The final report details the conditions for acceptance placed on the federal disposal project by the community of Dessel. Top priority is given to safety, health, and the environment. Two technical options are discussed. The need to maintain local participation and communication is affirmed, and the requirements for creating a positive impact and added value for the local community are detailed. The report closes with an insistence on getting clear commitments from the institutional actors.

POSSIBLE TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE LC PRODUCTS AND OUTPUTS

Initiation/continuity/improvement of dialogue

Recommendations/'local arguments' for decision-makers

Empowerment of your community in the decision-making process

Reports including expertise reports

Formal statements

Web pages, posters, newsletters, brochures, video etc. for dissemination

Good practices/methods for knowledge transfer

► In the LC forum, traditional divisions may be avoided more easily. Elected politicians here can step back from their usual role. Individuals can deliberate and vote as community members, not as party representatives. The LC also can offer a voice to interests that are not organized on a political level. Remember to be sure that your LC builds legitimacy through ensuring inclusive representation and expression. In that way you may best be sure that the important concerns of your community are addressed.

Among our working group members, different types of products, outputs and added value were delivered to their communities by LCs. In Belgium, for instance, MONA addressed questions posed by community members about the future impact of a waste repository. In Slovenia, an epidemiological baseline study uncovered community health issues that pre-existed the repository discussion. The LC took action to address these. In France, the CLIS de Bure sent recommendations to Parliament for the new law on RWM, telling how formal legal aspects of future LCs might be improved. ②③④ ■

③ **In Slovenia**, the Brežice LC ordered studies to meet public requests. They measured natural background radiation and compared the influence of the present NPP, checked for radioactivity in local produce, and studied cancer rates in the Brežice community in comparison with the population of Slovenia. This epidemiological study showed that the frequency of cancer has increased all over Slovenia and also in Brežice due to unhealthy lifestyle (fatty foods, lack of exercise and stress) and to population aging. But it was also found that there is significantly more cervical cancer among Brežice women (carcinoma colli uteri) while they consult gynecologists five to six times less than Slovenian women overall. Therefore the Brežice LC together with the national cancer prevention program ZORA sent special leaflets and invitations to consult, to all Brežice households.

④ **In France**, 5 delegates from the CLIS de Bure (representing both currents favorable and opposed to a repository) met with their Senators and the Industry Minister's cabinet with suggestions on how the new law on RWM should organize a future LC. The final legal text reflects these suggestions by enlarging representation to 8-10 more townships, creating a consultative group of medical and university specialists (in laboratory research, radiation protection and social sciences), and allowing the CLIS to become formalized as an association. While financing was not written into the law, assurances were received that funding would remain at current levels. However, the law does not clarify the LC mission as requested (the text remains open to interpretation as to the CLIS' ability to engage counter-expertise). Nor did the final text retain the requested formal voting procedures to designate a representative president and vice-president. Today's CLIS sees the 2006 law as relatively satisfactory, but awaits the government decree of application to learn what actual working conditions will be for the next generation of LC members.

② **In Belgium**, MONA compiled a list of frequently asked questions (FAQ) or active concerns about how a repository would impact the community over the next generations. MONA has developed proposals to deal with these concerns. The LC is bringing added value to the community by thinking now about how to address these future issues. A solid legal basis should be given to the solutions agreed now between the community and the authorities so that these solutions can survive over time. Here are examples of such FAQ along with MONA's proposals to address these concerns:

- ✓ Health: What if the health of my children, my grandchildren is affected by the repository? Who will be liable?
 - Create a special fund to deal with health issues
 - Establish an epidemiological baseline (detailed statistics on community health now) so comparisons can be made later
 - ✓ Who is liable for waste management?
 - Set up an insurance arrangement to be certain that waste owners or authorities will always be able to meet their responsibilities
 - Sign contracts making those responsibilities clear
 - ✓ What kind of compensation will the community receive?
 - The Socio-economic Development working group made detailed proposals for a "sustainability fund" and other longterm arrangements to keep the community growing and in good shape
 - ✓ What will happen in case of conflict between two authorities?
 - The LC came forward to examine and try to influence the "rules of the game"
-

Chapter 8

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATIONS: RELATIONS WITH OTHER PARTIES

Any LC is likely to be involved with the communication of information to the general public. The LC may have to identify the points of consensus and debate at a scientific level, and make them understandable to a wide audience. You have to inform inhabitants about your own role, work and conclusions. And you should get feedback on what the community thinks.

The LC's relations with outside parties will require careful consideration. A key early question concerns the kind of access you will give to your own proceedings: do you seek full transparency or do you retain certain restrictions and keep back certain documents?

The issue of relations with the media is also a prime concern. It is helpful if some communication professionals are LC members. In any event it is essential to learn how the media gather their news and to ensure that the LC can get useable information to them. It may be wise to get training or professional assistance with this.

If you have committee members who are also representatives of outside organizations, they should be responsible for "broadcasting" LC news to those communities or groups of origin—as well as for bringing back their input and reactions. The LC can be compared to the center of a ripple where the members of the LC can relay information out to the groups that they represent and so on. This work will be facilitated if the LC develops fact sheets, short summaries, and attractive materials that get people interested. ❶

If you are working in isolation and are relatively unknown by the community, what are the messages that you can give them? How can you get in touch with them? How far does this go? Is it possible for your LC to collaborate with other parties that have an interest in communicating about RWM governance or local decision-making in general? You might consider working with federations in order to "mutualize" resources and reach a larger audience.

Learning that there are shared views in the community can help LC members. You will gain confidence from knowing you are not alone, from being able to report that many citizens are thinking as you do. The LC needs a reliable mechanism for two-way information, and ways of measuring and tracking outside views. Consider too that the local community at the center of things must establish good working relations with other units of government. It is better to develop a unified view and position, and be able to count on the support of your neighbors and/or your region if they are contacted or have a role to play in the decision-making process. ❷

You will need to build a stepwise plan for communication with whoever is ►

❶ **In Belgium**, MONA found it important to keep lines of communication open with both the city council and with members' home organizations (clubs, associations). Members reported MONA's work, listened to reactions, and then brought feedback to the LC.

Practical examples of publicizing LC activities include the publication of a calendar, bags of bread with the MONA logo, publicity spots on the radio, development of a MONA board game to get youth involved, representation at the Christmas market and even MONA beer mats and bread wrappers. Questionnaire surveys were used to check that people were learning about MONA and whether they agreed with its work.

❷ **COWAM 2's working group** "Local Influence on the National Process" highlights this good practice: cooperation and side-by-side work with the different levels of government (community, district, region...) are needed in order to avoid fragmentation of local deliberations and weakening of their position.

► outside your committee at both the local and the larger level. This plan should make members' role clear, set the right times and places for informing important audiences, and determine how the LC will decide what messages should get across. You must foresee resources for producing materials and contacting the people who need to know about your work. The plan should also include means and milestones for checking with those outside that the LC is working well and in particular is properly representing the people it is meant to represent. You will need to evaluate too whether you are communicating effectively. ③

③ **In Spain**, the local information commission (CLI) of Almonacid de Zorita (Guadalajara) carries out public opinion polls to check success in informing civil representatives and area authorities about the functioning of the local NPP and about the programme for its closure and dismantling.

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION PLAN

Develop your plan early – what information to whom, when and how

Identify who is responsible for running and performing communications

Develop attractive materials that LC members can use with different audiences

Include means (e.g. survey) to check on:

how well the information is getting across

how well the LC is in tune with local feeling

Communication can be achieved through the local/national media. Internet can carry lots of information, but remember to alert people about your site and make them want to visit it. True bi-directional communication is sought through meetings and other ways of consulting and dialoguing.

Start communicating from the very beginning of local committee work. Different audiences should be targeted with tailored communication instruments, and you should ensure that there is adequate monitoring of your communication efforts with, for example, questionnaire-based surveys. ④

The LC can enter in contact with several types of bodies. Local and national NGOs can share information with the LC concerning the points they typically lobby for, and share experience in fostering dialogue with decision-makers. This may be particularly useful in countries where the local level traditionally has not been given much of a role in national planning. Bi-directional communication with political organizations may lead to an effective lobby for "local arguments" and to increased recognition of the LC. Targeting professional organizations is important to maintain relations with pertinent experts and ensure a good scientific level to the debate. ■

④ **In Hungary**, the WMPIA increases its visibility through newsletters, brief inserts in the press, a public information office, a video, school competitions, an "Information Park" (outdoor trail)... A regular "barometer" survey checks residents' knowledge of repository plans and WMPIA work. Local elected people gained high ratings for credibility as information sources. The survey found that scientists have less credibility. The association now attempts to build bridges between the public and science through a travelling exhibit, and through cooperation with experts at the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION FLOWS BETWEEN LC AND OTHER ACTORS

Chapter 9

EVALUATION

Evaluating the implementation and functioning of a Local Committee is a necessary task if we want to improve the LC. Awareness of the past allows us to face the future better armed. It is useful to focus on what has been done, to assess whether goals have been met, and to draw guidelines for reinforcing the efficiency and legitimacy of the LC.

By evaluation, we mean making systematic judgements about the LC's implementation and its results with reference to a set of criteria. Each chapter of the Roadmap covers an area that can be evaluated. Sample evaluation questions are listed below. A subgroup of the LC should get together to plan the evaluation. Starting from the sample list provided here the subgroup can develop more specific questions. Decisions will be needed, too, about "when and how" the evaluation is to be conducted, and "who" should give their viewpoint. Finally, the subgroup should be prepared to analyze the results and decide with the larger membership on actions to bring the LC closer to its desired goals. **1** ■

1 In France, the CLIS de Bure created a working group on the "Future of the LC" evaluating which aspects of its role and function could be carried forward in a new phase of RWM.

The national federation ANCLI, with the participation of the CLIS de Bure, developed a "White Paper on Local Governance of Nuclear Sites" analyzing a broad range of experience and making recommendations about all the aspects of LCs.

The Parliament published a report evaluating progress of all the players since the 1991 RWM law. This also –briefly and subjectively– evaluated the functioning of the CLIS de Bure and made some recommendations for procedure.

QUESTIONS YOU MIGHT ASK TO EVALUATE YOUR LC EXPERIENCE

Chapter 2: Does the mission of the LC correspond to community needs?

Chapter 3: Is the composition truly representative? Are the right persons on the LC?

Chapter 4: Is the LC able to meet its objectives? Were the resources (legal, human, financial...) adequate to meet these objectives? Were resources well used? Could better effects be obtained at the same cost?

Chapter 5: Does the daily work of the LC correspond to the stakes and steps of RWM? Is the communication between different levels of the LC successful? Do the members of the LC feel that their opinions are taken into account?

Chapter 6: Was needed information available? Was the dialogue format adequate? Was commissioned expertise useful? Did it have an impact outside the LC?

Chapter 7: Were products delivered as planned? Does the LC have an influence on the RWM decision-making process? Is the LC included in institutional procedures (public enquiries, EIA process...)? What added value does the community draw from the presence of the LC?

Chapter 8: Is external communication successful, especially in regard to local inhabitants? What are the relationships with other partners (local council, national representatives, RWM agency...)?

EVALUATION PROCEDURE

When? You need to know exactly when you want to make an evaluation of the LC: at the beginning, at the mid-term, at the end of its life-cycle? Several times? If the LC has different tasks or if it plays a role across different phases of a RWM project, perhaps small or large evaluations are needed at several checkpoints. Adaptation of the LC throughout the process may be necessary to fulfil its objectives.

Why? You need to clearly define the objectives of the evaluation and the target of evaluation (a general evaluation? evaluation of a specific LC initiative?)

How? You have to ensure that the tools used are adequate to the evaluation issues raised. A subgroup can prepare by developing questions to get concrete details about how the LC performs. Both "objective" (e.g. counting) and "subjective" (e.g. interviewing) measures may be appropriate. To develop workable, meaningful questions, and a plan for getting the information you need, it may be useful to get the help of a consultant (an academic or a person experienced in business evaluation).

Who? Two types of evaluation can be launched by the LC: a self-evaluation, and, an external evaluation. Both evaluations are useful, and may be organized at different times for different reasons. A third type of evaluation is launched by a third party. The LC has less control here. These three types of evaluation are described below.

Then what? When developing evaluation questions, keep in mind that you will want to act upon the answers you receive. Plan for discussion of what the answers tell you about your performance. It's likely that LC members will have concrete ideas for changes to be made (in format, strategy, operation). Set short-term and mid-term checkpoints to evaluate whether agreed changes or actions are really helping adjust LC performance to desired goals.

THREE TYPES OF EVALUATION

Self-evaluation performed by the LC

The self-evaluation gets the opinion of the members of the LC. They respond by themselves to the list of questions developed by the subgroup, and the results are discussed internally. Responding to some questions may involve collecting "objective" information (checking how the budget has been spent, counting how many meetings have been held or how many experts have been heard, etc.) "Subjective" points of view can be collected, too, for discussion. The self-evaluation can be a periodic check-up, including just a few questions to be sure the LC is on track and doing what it means to do. Or it can be a more formal and extensive operation, at a landmark point (each year of operation, or after a step in the RWM process). Then the LC will probably want to give a short report to its major stakeholders (local authorities...).

External evaluation requested by the LC

An external evaluation gets the opinion of LC members, but also asks partners and stakeholders how the LC is performing. It is conducted by an external party, and the results will tell the LC members how they are doing, but also give details to interested stakeholders (community residents, local or regional authorities, funding organisms...). It is important for the legitimacy of this evaluation that you choose an external evaluator who respects the principles of independence and transparency. It may be a consultant, or it may be a partner (the municipality...). The results of this evaluation will have more weight. Very likely the external evaluation should include both "objective" measures (counting hours spent, reports produced...) and "subjective" elements (interviews with LC members as well as with outside users or partners). Use this opportunity to communicate clearly what you need from others to get your job done correctly (funding, more human resources, more information from outside partners, clearer legal status...).

Third-party evaluation

When a third party launches or conducts an evaluation, the LC may have little control over the questions that are asked, who is asked, and how the results are reported. In this case it is probably wise to prepare a statement to be delivered to the oversight authorities, or reported in the press, or otherwise brought to the attention of important partners. In that statement you should make known your own evaluation results, reflections, and needs. This will balance the strong voice of the third-party evaluators. If all views are convergent, it may be easier to convince partners to facilitate desired changes. Get the help of your federation to publicize your viewpoint—especially if your LC feels that the third party has been unjustly severe in evaluation.

Conclusion

This Roadmap for Local Committee

Construction is the product of collaboration amongst stakeholders from across Europe: local elected people and community representatives, agents from national institutions and researchers. We are part of the strong new trend in Europe for communities to raise their voice in decision-making for the management of radioactive waste, through Local Committees. Our concern has been with "Implementing Local Democracy and Participatory Assessment Methods" and we believe our experience can be useful for others, whether they are concerned with waste management or other complex socio-technical decisions. We realized that we cannot designate a single path, but we could develop a Roadmap reflecting the diversity of our European landscape. The first chapter of our Roadmap showed indeed that each context is made up of a large number of disparate elements.

What general conclusions can we draw from our three-year examination (2004-2006) of our diverse experiences?

One way to pass on our experience is to draw out some sets of questions that you might usefully ask if you are considering forming, or even re-forming, a Local Committee (LC).

We learned that it is important from the outset to know who you are and what you initially wish to achieve. Components include a clear idea of the identity of the LC, whether it is to be a relatively passive transmitter of information or a more active negotiator in the decision-making process (DMP), and the development of a clear mission for the LC. Asking the right questions of your situation and formalizing your own analysis into a written mandate is a good start in getting your efforts taken into account in the DMP. A strong identity and role for the LC will be clear to national, regional and local decision-makers.

Worries over the likely legitimacy of a LC may concern people at the outset. Why should authorities take a local group seriously? Not all Local Committees are recognised by the political establishment and local participation may result from the spontaneous self-organization of concerned citizens. We found a spectrum of possible forms that may be considered legitimate and learned that many LC's are likely to start from an ad hoc form of thematic representation. Other types of representation can be developed as time passes, or the composition of the LC can be carefully worked out in advance with political parties, local organizations, and other "live forces" in the community. Even when the structure of the LC is determined by national law, it's necessary to compose a group of individuals who can represent their community and cooperate over many months or years. We saw the need to facilitate individuals' participation with sensitivity to their social and financial constraints. As in any effective organization, the LC will need proper regard for effective recruitment and retention of its members.

Equally we concluded that independent financial arrangements are vital. The LC must maintain its face in the community- any hint that it is "in the pay" of the implementer might destroy the hard work of the disinterested ▶

► volunteers. Clarity about the origin and sustainable sourcing of sufficient funds is essential. You can only participate if you have the means to do so and, because RWM issues are complex, you will require expertise that must be acquired or purchased. If there is a genuine will to empower the community to participate in the DMP sufficient funds must be earmarked to finance local involvement. We found that national and European federations are very useful as they mutualize resources, allow an important exchange of experience among members, and lobby national law- and decision-makers on behalf of the local perspective.

We noted that there is no standard blueprint for a LC but drew a partial list of questions that should enable you to devise/amend the LC structure. We also noted the need for flexibility in rules and procedures to deal with the evolution of the committee. Understanding the context in which you operate and reflecting that in your organizational procedures should enhance the effectiveness of your activities.

A key issue is the handling of information. Radioactive waste management is a complex topic with both technical and societal dimensions, and the LC plays a very important role in developing knowledge to help in decision-making. We clarified the differences between information, expertise, knowledge building and transfer. The main conclusion to be drawn is that you will need mechanisms for the LC members to get information, to acquire knowledge and to use it properly. In addition, since no single party can achieve everything alone, we conclude that you must continually work to build and maintain trust – trust in other parties and trustworthiness in your own activities. As ever, transparency and authenticity are bywords.

Your activities and your concrete output can lend significant added value not only to national decision-making but also to your community. We saw that some LCs take on a new life as an “extra tool for democracy” even when their original mission is completed.

Your communication of information to external agencies, including the public, requires careful consideration. The LC is the center of a ripple where the members relay information out to the groups that they represent and to the public and so on—and the LC must also check what those others think. The principal lesson is that this activity must be carefully planned, integrated into the procedures of the LC and evaluated for effectiveness, and we provided indications for a communication plan.

Finally we concluded that a thorough evaluation of the implementation and functioning of your entire programme was necessary for efficient functioning. We set out our suggested criteria for evaluation, by reviewing the topics touched on by each chapter of this Roadmap. Through evaluation, the best lessons of the past are integrated into plans for the future.

Throughout this Roadmap we have taken the point of view of the local community, and the persons who serve by participating in a Local Committee. We hope that our reflections and suggestions are helpful and we wish you all the best! ■

Annex 1

List of participating Local Committees

Members of the following local committees were active members of our working group. In Annex 2 we provide a list of all our members and other persons, from inside and outside COWAM 2, who contributed to our Roadmap.

MONA, MOL CONSULTATION ON NUCLEAR WASTE (BELGIUM)

The municipality of Mol, Belgium, is in the eastern part of Antwerp province about 60 km east of the city. The local partnership MONA was created in February 2000 to consider whether the municipality could accept a low and intermediate radioactive waste repository, and work out both technical and social aspects.

This committee was formed after the federal government instructed RWM agency NIRAS/ONDRAF to identify a method for integrating a repository project at the local level. The idea of local partnerships was developed to assure that every party that could be directly affected by a collective decision has an opportunity to express its opinions. The concept was developed by researchers from the University of Antwerp and the Luxemburg University Foundation. The idea was discussed with different local stakeholders and, on their recommendations, adapted to meet local needs.

MONA counted 36 members in its general assembly (including a NIRAS/ONDRAF representative), 12 in its executive committee and about 60 members in four working groups (see page 21). MONA received an annual budget from the RWM agency. The partnership was originally scheduled to last two years but members found that more time was needed. They handed their report to the Mol municipal council in January 2005. MONA's chairman stated : "Many anonymous volunteers spent their best efforts and their free time on this project. They do not invoke the 'NIMBY-doctrine' as an excuse but prefer instead to listen, study and build a carefully weighed case. Their findings will enable the community which they serve to evaluate and to decide."

www.monavzw.be

CSPI, SPECIAL PERMANENT COMMISSION FOR INFORMATION FOR THE COGEMA-HAGUE INSTALLATION (FRANCE)

Created in 1981 by decree of the Industry Minister, the CSPI is widely looked to as France's very first local committee in the nuclear sector. (Whilst the CSPI was originally connected to both the COGEMA reprocessing plant and the neighboring repository managed by ANDRA, the latter now has its own CLI or Local Information Commission.) Composed of about 38 members, the CSPI is run by the local/regional elected officials, and includes representatives of chambers, unions (including COGEMA workers' unions), environmental associations, independent laboratories, etc. COGEMA is not a member but sends a delegate. The CSPI is purely an information organ without any decision mandate. However, it is extremely active and has developed an extraordinary expertise for monitoring environmental releases and coordinating population health studies.

www.commission-hague.org

CLIS DE BURE, LOCAL COMMITTEE ON INFORMATION AND MONITORING CONNECTED WITH THE UNDERGROUND RESEARCH LABORATORY FOR HIGH-LEVEL RADIOACTIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT, BURE (FRANCE)

France's law of 1991 laid out a framework for research on potential options for the disposal of high-level and long-lived intermediate-level radioactive waste. The feasibility of deep geological disposal is investigated by implementer ANDRA using an underground research laboratory, constructed at Bure in the east of France. The CLIS was created by decree in 1999 when Bure was selected from among four candidate sites. The 1991 law specifies its role and frames its composition. The CLIS' mission is to assemble and disseminate information concerning RWM to the affected communities. As well, it follows the research activities and results of the laboratory and has the power to carry out counter-expertise. The CLIS is composed of representatives of the state and chambers of commerce and industry, industrial and agricultural unions (including lab workers' unions), environmental protection associations, as well as elected representatives (national and local). Because the township of Bure is located close to the border of two territorial units (departments), each of these as well as the General Council of the two administrative regions in which they lie is represented on the CLIS. Elected people from townships lying within 10 kilometers of the site are members, as is the director of the ANDRA laboratory (see page 21).

www.clis-bure.com

WMPIA, WEST MECSEK PUBLIC INFORMATION ASSOCIATION (HUNGARY)

Hungary's Boda Claystone Formation, a former mining site, has been under investigation since 1993 in view of hosting high level waste produced by the nearby Paks nuclear power plant. The next steps will be a site-specific characterization, and an environmental impact assessment (EIA) regarding an underground research laboratory (URL). Licensing and technical planning would then be followed by construction of the URL. The West Mecsek Public Information and Regional Development Association (WMPIA) was founded in 1996 and now counts 9 member communities. The missions of the WMPIA cover public information about the investigation process, monitoring of the process, raising environmental consciousness, and fostering development in the affected settlements. The association aims to heighten public acceptance of the process through improving knowledge. The association uses a range of information and involvement tools, including print and video newsletters, and school science and sport competitions.

In Hungary, there is a legal basis for the creation of LCs covering voting procedures and the mandate of members. Funding is covered by law and supported by state budgets. Following a recent change in the law the money received by the WMPIA is no longer restricted to "information provision" but can also be used for regional development purposes.

www.nymtit.hu

CLI DE VANDELLÒS-HOSPITALET DE L'INFANT (SPAIN)

There have been three CLI (Comisión Local de Información) in Vandellòs. The first was created in 1980 in response to the construction of the nuclear power plant (NPP) Vandellòs-II and comprised the City Hall, its technical advisers, including specialized lawyers, and managers of the construction programme. The second CLI was created to respond to the dismantling process of the NPP Vandellòs-I (1990-2003). The present committee has the aim of monitoring the operational aspects of the NPP Vandellòs-II. Its members represent the Town Halls of Vandellòs i l'Hospitalet de l'Infant, Pratdip, Montrou del Camp, l'Ametlla de Mar and Tivissa (15 people); Employment and Industry Regional Services (2 people); Environment Regional Service (1 person); secondary school (1 person); NPP managers (ANAV) (3 people); tourism and business sectors (2 people); local Health Service (2 people); Local press/media (2 people); Spanish Regulatory Body (CSN) (2 people) and a secretary. Its brief is to cover the demand for information with regard to the NPP and help maintain normal relations between the NPP and the neighboring citizens.

LOCAL COMMITTEE OF INFORMATION AND MONITORING FOR THE SHUT DOWN AND DISMANTLING OF THE "JOSE CABRERA" NPP, IN ALMONACID DE ZORITA MUNICIPALITY (SPAIN)

Almonacid de Zorita is a member of the Spanish Association of Municipalities (AMAC; see page 19) and is based in the area 10 kms from the Jose Cabrera NPP. The Zorita CLI (Comisión Local de Información) was promoted by AMAC on the basis of French and Swedish experience and was formed in response to the closing and dismantling process of the NPP. The CLI is chaired by the Town Hall of the municipality hosting the facility and comprises representatives of: neighboring municipalities; the facility owner; Spanish Regulatory Body (CSN); State and Regional Government; Provincial Administration; social representatives of the area; NPP employees and the national RWM company (ENRESA). The CLI meets twice a year, with additional meetings as necessary. It covers information provision and exchange on issues of safety (including emergency plans); information management (participation in RWM policies), and social and economic effects (compensations, identifying alternatives for economic development).

CERNAVODĂ AREA INFORMATION COMMITTEE (ROMANIA)

The district of Cernavodă extends 20 Km around Romania's nuclear power plant (NPP). Cernavodă City touches the plant restriction area (1 km) and has 20,000 citizens. The district counts another 10,000 inhabitants from the neighboring municipalities. An intermediary storage near the NPP keeps the spent fuel for 55 years until a final repository will be decided and built. One repository for low and intermediate waste is planned to be built also near the plant in the next few years.

The Area Information Committee was founded by local authorities who sent an invitation to all representatives of the extended community. The LC was formally created on October 21, 2004 as a protocol between local authorities (mayor of Cernavodă, local councilors) and 8 local NGO's. The LC's role is to ask for transparency, public information and participation in decision-making around the NPP and storage facilities, and promote economic and social development of the area. Communication with the people of Cernavodă takes place through local media (newspapers, radio, TV), in public meetings, and with local information sheets. The LC is not funded at all, and the local authority provides the only support: free rooms for meetings.

The LC has taken a primary role in bringing the Cernavodă area out of isolation. They have organized many official meetings including an international conference in April, 2006 with the support of GMF (see page 19) and the European Commission. Present were mayors and other representatives from all GMF countries to speak of each country's experience, as well as all the important nuclear institutions in Romania.

SLOVENIAN LOCAL PARTNERSHIPS

Three LC from Slovenia (region of Posavje) were represented in our working group. The "Local Partnerships" serve as an umbrella for all activities during site characterization and confirmation of potential sites for the storage of low and intermediate-level radioactive waste. The LPs provide the platform for decision-making by local stakeholders and for cooperation between the municipality and implementer ARAO. A steering or coordinating committee facilitates the participation and involvement of citizens.

LP in Sevnica: In February 2006 the municipal council approved the mayor's proposal to form a steering committee of 9 members. In the beginning of March a strong civil initiative opposed the decision on local community participation in site selection process. In March 2006 the local council decided to withdraw from the site selection process on the mayor's proposal, and implementer ARAO stopped all activities.

LP in Brežice: The steering committee with 9 members nominated by the municipality council (3 members), mayor (2), local people (2) and ARAO (2) was formed in March 2006. The local partnership accepted the site characterization program and started organizing thematic committees. The main aim was to provide all information to the residents regarding repository site selection in order to prepare the 2008 final decision. Activities carried out include: presentations for local villages, associations, unions; discussion circles on siting, repository design, radioactivity and administrative procedures; visits to the central interim storage facility in Ljubljana for all those interested; establishment of a permanent committee "Dečno Selo" to investigate the rumours of disposal of radioactive waste in one abandoned coal mine in the community; independent studies on public request (described on page 28). In May 2006 a strong civil initiative formed in the local community to oppose the siting activity. In the run-up to local elections (summer 2006) the municipal council decided to withdraw the precise location under study, but voted also to maintain the local partnership and to identify a new potential location. In late 2006 a new potential location was identified by ARAO, supported by local citizens and approved by the municipal council. As a consequence the steering committee will be reorganized, so local members more closely associated with the new potential location will take part.

LP in Krško: Krško is the site of the nuclear power plant and as such, is already the de facto host of radioactive waste. The mayor spearheaded a strong and clear involvement in the site selection process and creation of a local partnership, whose organizational structure is seen on page 21. The coordination committee has 15 members. The LC has prepared and adopted a program and formed working groups centered on sustainable development, technical issues, environment and health, limited land use, and consideration of the Aarhus Convention.

Annex 2

PARTICIPANTS in COWAM 2 – WP1 on “Implementing Local Democracy and Participatory Assessment Methods”

LOCAL COMMITTEES, COMMUNITIES, LOCAL GOVERNMENT, FEDERATIONS

Mol, *Belgium*

Bure, *France*

La Hague, *France*

Boda, *Hungary*

Cernavoda, *Romania*

Saligny, *Romania*

Brezice, *Slovenia*

Krško, *Slovenia*

Sevnica, *Slovenia*

Vandellòs, *Spain*

Amaraz, *Spain*

AMAC, *Spain*

MEDIA

RTV, *Slovenia*

REGULATORS, SAFETY AUTHORITIES

FANC, *Belgium*

MINISTRIES

Environment and Sustainable
Development, *France*

WASTE PRODUCERS

EdF, *France*

WASTE MANAGEMENT ORGANIZATIONS, IMPLEMENTERS

RAWRA, *Czech Republic*

ANDRA, *France*

ARAO, *Slovenia*

ENRESA, *Spain*

EXPERTS INSIDE THE NUCLEAR ESTABLISHMENT

SCK•CEN, *Belgium*

IRSN, *France*

INR, *Romania*

EXPERTS OUTSIDE THE NUCLEAR ESTABLISHMENT

University of Liège, "Spiral" Laboratory, *Belgium*

Institut Symlog, Paris, *France*

Technical University of Troyes, *France*

Institute of Sociology, Academy of Sciences, Budapest,
Hungary

Faculty of Arts, Sciences, Ljubljana, *Slovenia*

Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich, *Switzerland*

Lancaster University, *UK*

ALL THE MEMBERS OF WP1 participated actively in the discussions leading to the Roadmap. Further information was drawn from the COWAM 1 archives.

Special thanks to these WP1 members for their extra contributions to writing and development:

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Ludo Jadoul (FANC, *Belgium*)

Benoît Jaquet (CLIS de Bure, *France*)

Mariana Mircea (Cernavodă, *Romania*)

Luc Smeyers, Liesbet Vanhoof
(MONA, *Belgium*)

Nadja Železnik (ARAO, *Slovenia*)

We are grateful to all the other COWAM 2 stakeholder participants and Work Package leaders who commented on the Roadmap. These include stakeholders from Holland, Germany and the UK (countries not directly represented in WP1). We also thank Swedish stakeholders from COWAM 1. Finally, we appreciated thoughtful feedback by George Brownless (OECD NEA) and by Simon Webster (European Commission).

COWAM 2 was part-funded by the European Commission. Production of the Roadmap benefited from complementary funding by IRSN, France.

Claire Mays, Work Package 1 Leader (Institut Symlog, Paris, France)

Scientific reports available from WP1

Our group on "Implementing Local Democracy and Participatory Assessment" developed this Roadmap. We also requested studies on specific subjects from some of the researchers who participated in our group. Today you can visit the COWAM 2 website (www.cowam.org) to download reports about the entire COWAM 2 program, and also, the detailed WP1 reports summarized below.

THE "PARTICIPATORY TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT" THEME: TOOLS FOR INVOLVEMENT

PTA-1: Tools for Local Stakeholders in Radioactive Waste Governance: Challenges and Benefits of Selected Participatory Technology Assessment Techniques

Thomas Flüeler, Pius Krütli & Michael Stauffacher (ETH), Zürich

In radioactive waste governance it is recognized that different stakeholders and the general public need to be involved in the decision process. Yet, it is not evident what 'involvement' actually means and, consequently, which techniques might best facilitate public involvement. Based on a thorough literature review, we present selected techniques to associate stakeholders in decision-making about technology. We discuss selection criteria and develop a framework to guide local actors in their choices.

There is no one-size-fits-all technique; different ones should be prudently combined to complement each other. To guide selection, we consider both the decision process and the targeted intensity of involvement. The strategic decision-making process for radioactive waste management moves through phases of problem identification, formulation of RWM options and their assessment, and the subsequent choice amongst options. We show how each decision-making phase can accommodate a certain intensity of involvement ranging from information to consultation, active involvement, collaboration and finally, empowerment.

Two versions of the report are available. The long version details the scholarly literature about techniques. The short "toolbox" report includes a table of techniques, a three-step procedure for choosing among them, and seven "framing principles" or recommendations for local committees to enter their involvement under the best conditions.

PTA-2: Guidance on the Selection of PTA Tools for Stakeholders Involved in Radioactive Waste Governance

Erik Laes, Gaston Meskens (PISA; SCK•CEN), Belgium & Drago Kos (University of Ljubljana), Slovenia

In radioactive waste management governance social (or mutual) learning is often advocated as a means for reaching more 'acceptable' solutions to the radwaste problem. However, it is often not clear what 'social learning' actually means nor how one could achieve it. In this report we first clarify the concept of 'social learning' and distinguish between four different social learning goals: enhancing the capacity to justify positions, promoting the search for creative solutions, empowerment, and gaining access to scientific expertise. Next, taking the selection of PTA techniques developed in the PTA-1 report as a starting point, we investigate how well these techniques serve the social learning goals. We develop a simple comparative chart (called a 'lens') which allows stakeholders to choose a promising PTA technique adapted to the particular combination of social learning goals this stakeholder seeks to promote.

This report also details how Slovenian partners in COWAM 2 used one particular PTA technique (the 'focus group') in July 2005 to address the question of local democracy in RWM governance from the point of view of the communities. Three crucial themes emerged from the focus group discussion: a) What is an adequate knowledge base? b) What is a good information and communication strategy? c) How to avoid feelings of being sidelined in the decision-making process?

Taken together, these themes indicate areas where significant improvement in conditions for local democracy could be reached.

THE "CHECKING" THEME: CHECKING ON HOW PEOPLE FEEL ABOUT RADIOACTIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT

CHK-3: Investigating the Impact of Nuclear Information on Young People's Knowledge & Attitudes, by Using Different Methods/ Participatory Tools in an Educational Program

Marian Constantin, Daniela Diaconu (INR), Romania

Given that radioactive waste storage needs will be critical in Romania in about ten to fifteen years, younger generations, today in the 5-8th grade, should be prepared for the decision-making process. We investigated the impact of nuclear information on young people's knowledge & attitudes by using different methods in an educational program. We completed a baseline survey of six groups of middle school students, three each from Pitesti and Cernavodă early in 2005. After analysis an educational programme was developed including a detailed resource book and three classroom teaching options: classical lecture style; discovery method; simulation of a Local Committee. These are described in the report. Three groups from the towns of Pitesti and four from Cernavodă participated in the program and completed a new questionnaire measurement in May 2006. The main conclusions were: a) Even though the programme raised awareness of some dangers associated with radioactive wastes the level of acceptance remained high and constant; b) An interdisciplinary course should be introduced in national curricula covering energy alternatives, pollution, safety, security of energy supply, radiation types and radioactivity including NPP and RW repository aspects; c) For localities with nuclear facilities, youngsters may readily participate in activities such as the simulation of a Local Committee, debates, discussions, visits, etc.

CHK-4: Genesis of an Approach: From Public Non-Participation to Participation in a LILW Site Selection Process in Slovenia

Marko Polic, Drago Kos (University of Ljubljana) & Nadja Železnik (ARAO), Slovenia

Searching for a location for risky or unpleasant objects is a complex and difficult task. Slovenia has been searching for a location for a low and intermediate-level waste (LILW) repository for a number of years. The highly-illustrated report recounts the efforts in this direction, scrutinizing all their diversity, weaknesses and successes. The main problem in the site search for this facility has been social acceptability; the most important step was the transition from a purely technical approach to an approach that involves local people in the decision processes. The report explains critical changes in the search process and also relates them to national changes in political regime. Public opinion closely reflected these changes, sometimes also generating them. Formerly highly negative attitudes toward RWM matters are slowly being replaced by less negative ones, while the participation of local people is increasing.

This Roadmap for Local Committee Construction

is the product of collaboration amongst stakeholders from across Europe: local elected people and community representatives, agents from national institutions and researchers. We are part of the strong new trend in Europe for communities to raise their voice in decision-making for the management of radioactive waste, through Local Committees. As participants in the European research project COWAM 2 (2004-2006), our concern has been with "Implementing Local Democracy and Participatory Assessment Methods". We believe our experience can be useful for others, whether they are concerned with waste management or other complex socio-technical decisions. We realized that we cannot designate a single path, but our Roadmap could reflect the diversity of experience found in our different contexts.

How is an inclusive, democratic decision-making or information process achieved in the communities? And what are the best ways to achieve it? What is the experience of communities now dealing with waste management decisions? And what do they recommend to communities who may start to deal with these in the future?

Generally a Local Committee (LC) is formed to respond to the waste question in the community and to advise the decision-makers and ensure that local views are taken into account before decisions are made on technological, economic and societal topics.

Why "Local Committee" (LC) ?

Our COWAM 2 working group decided that we should produce a Roadmap for Local Committee Construction. This Roadmap results from discussions and collaborations throughout the three years of COWAM 2. It reflects the collective wisdom of the forty WP1 participants. Boxed illustrations highlight our local experience. The list of all those who contributed is found at the end of the Roadmap.

By informing communities—whether they be townships, regions, or other groupings—about choices and experience in the formation of Local Committees, this Roadmap has the potential to improve the governance of radioactive waste management.

Why a "Roadmap for Local Committee Construction" ?

The Roadmap targets local communities and takes their point of view, but we anticipate that other players will read it.

It is intended to be useful to both:

- ✓ *Communities who are building a Local Committee (LC) from the ground up, who may (or may not) have a pretty large degree of liberty to define what they want to do. The Roadmap identifies the main issues that the community decision-makers may want to address in their design planning (and possibly, in their negotiation with other players).*
- ✓ *Existing LCs who want to refine their practice or reposition themselves. The Roadmap highlights what these LCs could enhance.*

Who should read the Roadmap?